

RAJA NARENDRALAL KHAN WOMEN'S COLLEGE (AUTONOMOUS)

NATIONAL SEMINAR

on

Wetlands and Traditional Knowledge: Celebrating Cultural Heritage

Sponsored by

**State Wetlands Authority, Department of Environment
Govt. of West Bengal**

**World
Wetlands Day**
February 2026

Wetlands and traditional
knowledge: Celebrating
cultural heritage

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Jointly Organised

by

Postgraduate Department of Zoology

and

Postgraduate Department of Geography

Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous)

Midnapore-721102, West Bengal

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Midnapore-721102, West Bengal

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VIDYASAGAR UNIVERSITY

Date: 03.02.2026

MESSAGE

I am delighted to learn that the Postgraduate Department of Zoology and the Postgraduate Department of Geography of Raja Narendra Lal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Midnapore are jointly going to organize a National Seminar on *Wetlands and Traditional Knowledge: Celebrating Cultural Heritage*, sponsored by the State Wetlands Authority, Department of Environment, Government of West Bengal to be held on 10th February, 2026 at the College premises. I extend my warm greetings and best wishes to the organizers, participants, scholars and students associated with this timely and meaningful academic initiative.

This national seminar provides an excellent platform for academicians, researchers, policymakers and students to engage in critical dialogue, exchange ideas and explore interdisciplinary perspectives on wetlands, conservation practices, and traditional ecological knowledge. Wetlands are among the most productive yet fragile ecosystems, playing a vital role in biodiversity conservation, climate regulation and sustaining livelihoods. Equally important is the vast reservoir of traditional knowledge, evolved over generations, which reflects a harmonious relationship between human societies and nature. The integration of scientific understanding with indigenous wisdom is crucial for sustainable environmental management and for preserving our rich cultural heritage.

I commend Raja Narendra Lal Khan Women's College (Autonomous) for its consistent commitment to academic excellence, research and social relevance. I am confident that the deliberations of this seminar will generate valuable insights and constructive recommendations that will contribute meaningfully to scholarship, policy formulation and community awareness.

I wish the seminar every success and hope it will inspire sustained research and collaborative efforts in the field of environmental conservation and cultural studies.

Dipak Kumar Kar

(Professor Dipak Kumar Kar)

Dr. Swapna Ghorai,
Principal, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous),
& Convener, National Seminar Organizing Committee.

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Message

Date: 08.02.2026

It gives me immense pleasure to extend a warm welcome to all scholars, researchers, students, and distinguished participants to the National Seminar on “Wetlands and Traditional Knowledge: Celebrating Cultural Heritage”, organized as part of the World Wetlands Day Observation 2026 by Raja Narendralal Khan Women’s College (Autonomous). This seminar, jointly organized by the Postgraduate Department of Zoology and the Postgraduate Department of Geography, reflects our institution’s continued commitment to academic excellence and societal relevance.

Wetlands are among the most productive ecosystems on Earth, sustaining biodiversity, supporting livelihoods, and preserving rich reservoirs of traditional knowledge developed through generations of human–nature interaction. In an era of rapid environmental change, revisiting indigenous practices and community wisdom is crucial for achieving sustainable wetland management and conservation.

I am confident that this seminar will provide a vibrant platform for interdisciplinary dialogue, knowledge exchange, and critical reflection on the ecological, cultural, and policy dimensions of wetlands. I sincerely acknowledge the generous support of the State Wetland Authority, Department of Environment, Government of West Bengal, whose funding has made this academic endeavour possible.

I congratulate the organizing departments for their initiative and wish the seminar every success, hoping it will inspire meaningful research, collaboration, and action towards wetland conservation.

With best wishes,

Dr. Swapna Ghorai
Principal & Convener
Organizing Committee

National Seminar on
“Wetlands and Traditional Knowledge: Celebrating Cultural Heritage”
PG Department of Zoology & PG Department of Geography
Raja Narendralal Khan Women’s College (Autonomous), Midnapore-722102

DR. SWAPNA GHORAI
Principal

Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College
(Autonomous)
Midnapore, West Bengal

About the Seminar

The National Seminar on “Wetlands and Traditional Knowledge: Celebrating Cultural Heritage” is being organized as part of the World Wetlands Day Observation 2026 by Raja Narendralal Khan Women’s College (Autonomous), jointly by the Postgraduate Departments of Zoology and Geography. The seminar aims to highlight the ecological significance of wetlands alongside the rich traditional knowledge and cultural practices that have evolved around these ecosystems over generations.

Wetlands play a crucial role in biodiversity conservation, water regulation, climate resilience, and livelihood support. Equally important is the indigenous and community-based knowledge that has historically guided the sustainable use and management of these fragile ecosystems. In the present context of environmental degradation and climate change, integrating traditional wisdom with scientific research has become essential for effective wetland conservation and policy formulation.

This national-level academic forum seeks to bring together researchers, academicians, students, and practitioners from diverse disciplines to engage in meaningful discussions on wetland ecology, cultural heritage, conservation strategies, and sustainable management practices. The seminar also encourages young scholars and students to explore interdisciplinary perspectives and community-oriented approaches in environmental studies.

The seminar is generously funded by the State Wetland Authority, Department of Environment, Government of West Bengal, whose support has enabled the organization of this academic initiative. We sincerely hope that the deliberations and interactions during the seminar will contribute to enhanced understanding, collaborative research, and informed action towards the conservation of wetlands and their associated cultural heritage.

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Dr. Pravat Kumar Shit
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“Wetlands and Traditional Knowledge: Celebrating Cultural Heritage”

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2. Dr. Pravat Kumar Shit

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Wetland: A Glorified Ecotone

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ABSTRACT

An ecotone is a transitional zone between two or more ecosystems. A wetland, however, represents a distinctive ecotone between terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. This zone is characterised by waterlogged conditions, hydric soils, and specialised vegetation adapted to periodic or permanent inundation. Owing to its nutrient-rich environment, a wetland exhibits a pronounced edge effect, supporting a wide range of plant, animal, and microbial species drawn from both adjoining ecosystems. Consequently, wetlands are recognised as among the most biodiverse ecosystems on Earth, often compared with tropical rainforests and coral reefs in terms of the concentration and variety of life they sustain.

Wetlands occur in various forms, including rice fields, ponds, bogs, lakes, rivers, estuaries, marshes, swamps, peatlands, and small canals, where water may be present seasonally or permanently. Since wetlands depend fundamentally on water to express their characteristic features, they are strongly influenced by rainfall, tidal action, and snowmelt. During the monsoon season, wetlands often appear as large, continuous water bodies, making it difficult to identify the individual pockets that become isolated during winter and summer. These isolated patches may be termed *meta-wetlands* and represent the most vital components of rain-fed wetland systems.

Meta-wetlands play a crucial role in sustaining flora and fauna during dry periods. These small water-holding pockets ensure the survival of organisms within an extended wetland landscape that becomes fully connected only during the monsoon. In tropical countries, particularly in India, species diversity, abundance, and richness in wetlands are largely regulated by these meta-wetland pockets. They provide organisms with opportunities to adopt bet-hedging strategies, allowing normal biological processes to continue and enabling recolonisation of the larger wetland system with the onset of the monsoon. Wetlands are reservoirs of immense biological wealth, along with valuable non-living components. They constitute essential natural resources that contribute to national economies and provide critical habitats for rare and endangered species. For this reason, wetlands of international importance are designated as Ramsar Sites and conserved under global conservation programmes. Without wetlands, migratory birds would lose their feeding and breeding grounds, and the absence of such habitats in tropical regions could accelerate the extinction of numerous bird species. Equally important is the maintenance of wetland food chains. From primary producers to higher-level consumers, meta-wetlands act as regulatory units that sustain ecological balance. Without viable populations of key biological components, the sustainability of wetland ecosystems cannot be ensured. Therefore, it is imperative to protect meta-wetlands from human interference during the dry seasons of winter and summer. Local communities must be sensitised to understand that wetlands are indispensable not only for present human survival but also for future generations. In essence, wetlands function as seed banks for human society and the natural world alike.

Keywords: *Wetland Ecotone; Biodiversity; Meta-wetlands; Ecosystem Sustainability*

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Wetlands as Cultural Landscapes and Heritage: Living Traditions and Traditional Ecological Knowledge

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands are not merely ecological systems, they are living cultural landscapes shaped by centuries of interaction between human communities and nature. Across the world, wetlands have sustained civilizations by providing water, food, medicine, transport routes, and fertile land. It also nurturing rich cultural traditions, beliefs, and indigenous knowledge systems. These landscapes embody Traditional Ecological Knowledge, a cumulative body of wisdom, practices, and innovations developed by local and indigenous communities through long-term observation and stewardship of wetland environments. Wetland based cultures have evolved sophisticated methods of fishing, farming, flood management, and biodiversity conservation that are both adaptive and sustainable. Practices such as seasonal harvesting, floating agriculture, community managed fisheries, and the protection of sacred water bodies demonstrate how cultural values and ecological principles are closely intertwined. Songs, folklore, rituals, festivals, and oral histories associated with wetlands reflect deep respect for water, wildlife, and the cyclical rhythms of nature, reinforcing conservation through cultural continuity. Today due to rapid urbanization, climate change, pollution, and unsustainable resource use, both wetlands and the traditional knowledge systems linked to them are increasingly at risk. The degradation of wetlands results not only in ecological loss but also in the erosion of cultural identities, livelihoods, and intergenerational knowledge transmission. Considering wetlands as cultural heritage sites emphasizes the need to conserve both their biological diversity and the human traditions that sustain them. Integrating Traditional Ecological Knowledge with modern scientific approaches offers a powerful framework for sustainable wetland management and climate resilience. By valuing wetlands as living heritage landscapes, conservation efforts can become more inclusive, culturally sensitive, and effective. Protecting these ecosystems therefore means safeguarding the wisdom, traditions, and cultural identities that have long ensured their survival, making wetlands a vital link between nature, culture, and sustainable futures.

World Wetlands Day 2026 came with the theme *Wetlands and Traditional Knowledge: Celebrating Cultural Heritage*. India's wetlands highlight how traditional wisdom has long guided sustainable relationships between people and water. Long before modern policies, communities developed practices that supported food security, regulated water, and protected wetlands through everyday cultural life. Despite global wetland losses, many wetlands have survived for centuries because people learned to live with water rather than control it. This principle lies at the heart of the Ramsar Convention's idea of *wise use*, which views wetlands as interconnected social-ecological systems. Protecting wetlands therefore means not only conserving ecosystems but also safeguarding the traditional knowledge and cultural heritage that sustain them.

Keywords: *Wetlands as Cultural Landscapes; Traditional Ecological Knowledge; Living Heritage; Indigenous Practices; Sustainable Wetland Management*

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Wetlands as Hydrological Systems: Groundwater Recharge and Agricultural Sustainability

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands are fundamental components of hydrological systems, providing essential ecosystem services that directly support groundwater recharge, agricultural sustainability, and water security. Recognized under the Ramsar Convention as ecosystems of international importance, wetlands regulate hydrological cycles by storing floodwaters, facilitating aquifer recharge, maintaining base flows, and improving water quality. These functions are critical for sustaining agriculture in water-stressed and monsoon-dependent regions where groundwater forms the backbone of irrigation and rural livelihoods.

This paper examines wetlands as hydrological assets within agricultural landscapes, emphasizing their role in soil moisture regulation, drought mitigation, and stabilization of groundwater tables. Wetlands support diverse agricultural systems, including irrigated farming, flood-recession agriculture, and traditional cropping practices that align with seasonal hydrological rhythms. In addition, wetlands contribute to nutrient retention and sediment control, thereby enhancing soil fertility and reducing the long-term impacts of agricultural runoff on downstream ecosystems.

Despite their importance, wetlands are increasingly degraded due to land-use conversion, drainage, over-extraction of groundwater, and fragmented water governance. Such pressures undermine Ramsar objectives related to the wise use of wetlands and compromise national and regional policy goals on sustainable agriculture, climate resilience, and water management. Climate change further intensifies these challenges by increasing hydrological variability and the frequency of extreme events.

Aligned with Ramsar's "wise use" principle and integrated water resources management (IWRM) frameworks, this paper highlights the need for policy coherence that links wetland conservation with agricultural planning and groundwater regulation. Emphasis is placed on wetland restoration, landscape-level management, participatory governance, and the integration of wetland values into agricultural and water policies. Strengthening science-policy-community interfaces is essential for recognizing wetlands not as marginal lands but as strategic hydrological systems vital for sustainable agriculture and long-term water security.

Keywords: *Wetland Hydrology; Groundwater Recharge; Agricultural Sustainability; Integrated Water Resources Management; Ramsar Wise Use*

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Wetlands as Carbon Stores: Blue Carbon Ecosystems and Climate Change Mitigation

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands are among the most efficient natural carbon sinks, playing a critical role in climate change mitigation through long-term carbon sequestration and storage. Often referred to as blue carbon ecosystems, wetlands—including marshes, peatlands, floodplains, and mangroves—capture atmospheric carbon dioxide through high primary productivity and store it in vegetation and waterlogged soils for centuries. This capacity makes wetlands disproportionately important in regulating global carbon cycles relative to their spatial extent.

This lecture examines the role of wetlands as carbon stores and their contribution to climate change mitigation, with particular emphasis on inland and coastal blue carbon ecosystems. It highlights the biogeochemical processes that enable wetlands to function as stable carbon reservoirs, such as anaerobic soil conditions, slow decomposition rates, and sediment accumulation. The discussion also addresses how wetland degradation, drainage, and land-use change can transform these ecosystems from carbon sinks into significant sources of greenhouse gas emissions.

The presentation situates wetland carbon dynamics within the broader framework of climate policy, including their relevance to Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs), nature-based solutions (NbS), and international agreements such as the Paris Agreement and the Ramsar Convention. Emphasis is placed on the need to integrate wetland conservation and restoration into climate mitigation strategies, land-use planning, and carbon accounting mechanisms.

By linking scientific understanding with policy frameworks, the lecture underscores the importance of protecting and restoring wetlands as cost-effective, multifunctional climate solutions. Recognizing wetlands as vital blue carbon ecosystems not only strengthens climate mitigation efforts but also delivers co-benefits for biodiversity conservation, water regulation, and community resilience in the face of accelerating climate change.

Keywords: *Blue Carbon Ecosystems; Wetland Carbon Sequestration; Climate Change Mitigation; Nature-based Solutions; Carbon Storage*

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Wetlands in India: Past, Present, and Future

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands in India often referred to as the "kidneys of the landscape," represent a vital intersection of hydrological processes, biological diversity, and cultural heritage. Spanning diverse ecoclimatic regimes—from high-altitude Himalayan lakes to coastal mangroves—these ecosystems cover approximately 16.89 million hectares, or 5.12% of the national landmass. Historically, Indian wetlands were managed through sophisticated community-led systems and spiritual reverence, viewing water as a sacred element essential for life. However, colonial-era perspectives and modern development shifted this paradigm, often treating wetlands as "wastelands" to be drained for agriculture.

Currently, Indian wetlands face a "devastating truth": nearly 40% of natural wetlands have vanished over the last three decades due to urbanization, agricultural encroachment, and pollution. Despite these losses, India has demonstrated significant international leadership, expanding its Ramsar Site network to 98 sites by February 2026—the largest in Asia. Modern conservation is driven by decentralized legal frameworks like the Wetlands (Conservation and Management) Rules, 2017, and flagship initiatives such as Amrit Dharohar and MISHTI, which link ecological restoration with green jobs and carbon sequestration.

Looking toward the future, the Anthropocene poses critical challenges, including sea-level rise in the Sundarbans and glacial retreat in the Himalayas, alongside the rapid spread of invasive alien species. To secure these ecosystems, a paradigm shifts toward basin-scale planning (the WISER 2025 framework) and the legal recognition of wetlands as "living entities" is required. This article highlights the urgent need to bridge the gap between high-resolution geospatial monitoring and ground-level enforcement to ensure the long-term water and ecological security of the nation.

Keywords: *Indian Wetlands; Ramsar Sites; Wetland Conservation Policy; Hydrological and Biodiversity Functions; Future Climate Challenges*

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**Wetlands as Archives of Ecological Memory: Traditional Ecological Knowledge,
Landscape, and Identity in Jhargram, West Bengal**

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands have conventionally been understood within environmental sciences as fragile ecological systems that support biodiversity and regulate hydrological cycles. However, such approaches often marginalize the cultural, mnemonic, and epistemological dimensions through which landscapes are inhabited and sustained by indigenous and rural communities. This paper examines wetlands in the Jhargram region of West Bengal as biocultural landscapes, arguing that they are produced through the interaction of ecological processes, collective memory, and Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK). Drawing upon theoretical insights from cultural ecology, environmental anthropology, and memory studies, the study demonstrates how wetlands function simultaneously as ecological habitats, mnemonic sites, and markers of cultural identity among indigenous communities. The paper further explores how modernization, land-use change, and the erosion of oral traditions threaten both ecological sustainability and cultural continuity. By foregrounding local knowledge systems as epistemologically valid, the study calls for an integrative model of conservation that recognizes wetlands not merely as ecosystems but as lived and remembered landscapes.

Keywords: *Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK); Wetland Landscapes; Cultural landscape; Indigenous Knowledge Systems; Biocultural Heritage; Environmental Memory; Landscape and Identity; Wetlands; Jhargram.*

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**Impact of Urbanization on Wetland Degradation and Habitat Quality: A Case Study of
New Town, Kolkata**

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ABSTRACT

Rapid urban expansion has become one of the most significant drivers of wetland degradation in peri-urban landscapes of developing countries. This study examines the spatio-temporal dynamics of land use/land cover (LULC) change and its impact on wetland ecosystems within the New Town Planning Area (NTPA) over the last three decades (1995–2025). Using multi-temporal satellite imagery, machine learning (ML), and deep learning (DL) models. The study quantifies the changes in wetlands and evaluates associated habitat quality and ecosystem services (ESS). Advanced classification techniques were employed to analyse historical LULC transitions, while predictive modelling was applied to project future land cover scenarios for 2050 and 2070. The results exhibit a sharp decline of wetlands during the past three decades, due to population growth, infrastructure development, land use change and the boom of urbanization. Habitat quality assessment further indicates a continuous degradation of wetland quality, including biodiversity loss and climate change. Projections suggest that this will increase further by 2050 and 2070, posing serious ecological and environmental challenges for sustainable wetland management. These findings on the spatio-temporal changes of wetlands and ESS can inform wetland decision-making processes and facilitate effective conservation, protection, and restoration of wetlands for the sustainability of the area.

Keywords: *Urbanization; Wetland Degradation; Habitat Quality; Machine Learning; Deep Learning.*

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Assessing Land-Use and Land-Cover Dynamics in the Mashi Dam Command Area:

A Geospatial Approach

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ABSTRACT

This research examines the spatio-temporal dynamics of land-use and land-cover (LULC) changes in the Mashi Dam command area of Rajasthan, India, from 1988 to 2018, with projections up to 2041. Leveraging satellite imagery from Landsat 5, LISS-3, and Sentinel 2A MSI, the study conducted a detailed assessment of LULC alterations across a 90.07 km² area. Rigorous validation of the 2018 land cover map against ground-truth data ensured the reliability of the predictions, which were subsequently utilized to forecast future LULC patterns. The analysis uncovered significant impacts on cropland, barren land, built-up areas, and scrub land throughout the study period. From 2008 to 2018, built-up areas, water bodies, and barren land exhibited substantial growth, while cropland experienced a decline of 4.75%. Projections indicate a further reduction in cropland by 2041, accompanied by an expansion of barren land. These findings underscore the critical need for effective land management strategies to mitigate the conversion of productive land into barren areas, thereby ensuring the sustainable utilization of agricultural resources in the region. The integration of geospatial and remote sensing technologies was pivotal in comprehending these LULC dynamics and formulating strategies for future natural resource management. The study's insights can inform policymakers and land administrators in addressing the challenges posed by land transformation and promoting sustainable development.

Keywords: *Land-use and land-cover, Spatio-temporal dynamics, Remote sensing, Sustainable land management, Mashi Dam.*

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**Analyzing Wetland Hydrology and Floodwater Dynamics in the Lower Shilabati River
Basin, Ghatal Sub-Division, West Medinipur, Eastern India**

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands in monsoon-dominated river basins play a critical role in regulating floodwater, sustaining groundwater recharge, and promoting ecological and agricultural processes. Recurrent seasonal flooding in the lower Shilabati River basin in the Paschim Midnapore district of West Bengal is sometimes viewed as a calamity, although it is inextricably tied to the hydrological functioning of its vast floodplain wetlands. The present study scrutinizes wetland hydrology and surface–subsurface water dynamics in the lower Shilabati basin, with particular emphasis on the interaction between river flooding, wetland storage, and groundwater systems. Seasonal variations in water levels, flood inundation patterns, and wetland connectivity were analyzed using field observations, hydrological data, and spatial analysis. Results indicate that wetlands act as temporary floodwater storage zones during peak monsoon periods, attenuating flood peaks and facilitating delayed release of water to adjacent agricultural lands and aquifers. Prolonged inundation contributes to groundwater recharge and enhances soil moisture availability during the post-monsoon and dry seasons. However, rapid land-use change, wetland encroachment, and inadequate floodwater management have reduced the natural buffering capacity of these wetlands, exacerbating flood impacts in recent years. The study highlights the need to recognize wetlands as functional hydrological components rather than flood-prone wastelands. Integrating wetland conservation with flood management and irrigation planning can transform recurrent flooding into a valuable water resource, thereby improving regional water security and enhancing resilience to climate variability in the lower Shilabati basin.

Keywords: *Wetland hydrology; Flood dynamics; Floodplain wetlands; Monsoon flooding; Shilabati River basin; Water resource management*

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The Role of Wetland on Livelihood of Marginalized Section of Community: A Case Study on Three Panchayat Samities under Uluberia Subdivision in Howrah District of West Bengal, India

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ABSTRACT

The study makes an attempt to identify and analyze the factors which influence the household use of wetlands in Howrah District of West Bengal, India. A few wetlands were selected from three Panchayat Samities namely, Bagnan-I, Bagna-II and Bainan under Uluberia Subdivision in Howrah District of West Bengal, which are used by local people for multiple purposes. Probit models are used for the identification of the factors explaining household dependency on wetland. The results indicate that the poor, landless, from lower social classes, and have low education levels are more inclined to utilize wetland resources than those in better circumstances. Families with a larger number of members are more likely to gather greater quantities of wetland resources. Nevertheless, households from higher castes have greater access to the wetlands for irrigation purposes. The findings suggest that wetlands are essential or play a vital role for the survival of underprivileged groups within the community.

Keywords: *Wetland products, Dependency, Livelihood, Probit Model*

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Glacial Retreat in the Himalayas: Geospatial Monitoring and Modeling of Hydro-climatic Impacts

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ABSTRACT

This research investigates the dynamics and implications of glacier retreat in the Dhauladhar Range of Himachal Pradesh, emphasizing their critical role in regional hydrology and climate signalling. Glaciers, which store approximately 69% of the Earth's freshwater, are increasingly sensitive to climate change, as evidenced by negative mass balance trends reported in recent decades. Utilizing Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and remote sensing (RS) technologies, this research quantifies variations in Area Accumulation Ratio (AAR), Equilibrium Line Altitude (ELA), and Specific Mass Balance over the studied period from 2000 to 2026. Findings indicate a significant decline in AAR from 0.17 km² in 2000 to 0.10 km² by 2026, correlating with rising temperatures and altered precipitation patterns. Specific mass balance estimates demonstrate a downward trend, with values ranging from -0.984 in 2000 to -1.121 in 2026. This decline reflects a concerning acceleration in glacier melting, with implications for regional water supply and ecosystem sustainability. The retreat of glaciers threatens freshwater availability for downstream communities, exacerbating water resource challenges in the region. The study underscores the need for continuous monitoring and adaptive management strategies to mitigate the impacts of climate change on these critical water resources. By integrating climate data with glacier dynamics, this research contributes to a better understanding of the interactions influencing glacial behavior and supports informed decision-making for sustainable resource management in the context of ongoing environmental change.

Keywords: *Glacier Dynamics, Area Accumulation Ratio (AAR), Mass Balance, NDSI, Dhauladhar Range.*

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Beyond the Reeds: Reclaiming Wetlands as Living Libraries of Indigenous Wisdom and Cultural Heritage

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands are far more than stagnant pools or ecological buffers; they are the "liquid archives" of human history. For millennia, Indigenous communities have viewed these ecosystems not as wilderness to be conquered, but as Cultural Landscapes essential to their identity, spirituality, and survival. While modern science often isolates "nature" from "culture," this paper argues that the health of our global wetlands is inextricably linked to the preservation of Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK). This study examines how Indigenous practices—such as the calculated cultivation of aquatic fibers and the spiritual governance of water rights—have historically maintained the delicate equilibrium of marshlands. By framing wetlands as Heritage Sites, we challenge the conventional "hands-off" conservation approach. Instead, we demonstrate through a series of global case studies that active Indigenous stewardship often results in higher biodiversity and greater climate resilience than state-led protection alone. Our findings suggest that the degradation of wetlands is a direct consequence of "cultural amnesia"—the systematic decoupling of traditional practices from land management. To reverse this, we propose a transformative policy framework that integrates ancestral memory with modern hydrological science. This "Two-Eyed Seeing" approach ensures that wetlands remain both ecologically vibrant and culturally significant. Ultimately, saving the marsh requires us to honor the voices of those who have listened to its waters for centuries.

Keywords: *Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK), Cultural Landscapes, Indigenous Stewardship, Wetland Heritage, Socio-Ecological Resilience.*

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The Role of Wetlands in Sustaining Rural Livelihoods: A Socio-Economic Perspective

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands provide a backbone to the economy of rural areas by providing many different sources of economic support as well as ensuring that communities within these rural environments stay stable, both socially and economically. Wetlands are crucial to many rural economies because they provide all the benefits of a natural food supply, since they act as biological supermarkets that produce food in an integrated food chain, thereby supporting many people. Wetlands support rural communities through fishing (small-scale) and through the use of fertile flood plains for agricultural production. In addition to agricultural production, there are many different types of items that can be harvested and utilized by rural communities from wetlands. These items include (but are not limited to) medicinal plants, reeds, and animal food. Because so many people in rural areas rely heavily on wetlands for their livelihoods, wetlands are critical to the food security of rural populations (particularly those populations living in developing countries) and provide employees in rural communities with work opportunities when there are lean times in agriculture and during difficult issues related to the climate in these communities (e.g. droughts, floods). In addition to providing food security and employment, wetlands also provide their users with a wide range of 'ecosystem services' (such as natural water purification and recharge of aquifers) that rural populations use for drinking water and livestock maintenance. Although low elevation areas receiving relatively large quantities of precipitation are identified as wetlands, wetlands are threatened by excessive land use, over-exploitation of wetland resources, and climate change.

Keywords: *Availability of food; Economy to make a living; Rural communities*

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Guardians of the Tide: Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) and Indigenous Resilience in the Sundarbans

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ABSTRACT

The Sundarbans, the world's largest contiguous mangrove forest, represents a complex socio-ecological landscape where human survival is inextricably linked to the pulse of the tides. This paper examines the Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) and indigenous practices of the forest-dependent communities—specifically the Moula (honey collectors), Bawali (woodcutters), and Jeley (fishers)—who have navigated this high-risk environment for generations.

Central to their survival is a unique syncretic belief system, epitomized by the worship of Bonbibbi, the forest deity. This spiritual framework serves as an informal regulatory mechanism, instilling a "code of conduct" that prevents over-exploitation and promotes a reciprocal relationship between humans and the apex predator, the Bengal tiger. Unlike rigid top-down conservation models, indigenous practices in the Sundarbans are characterized by seasonal harvest rotation, selective extraction, and the maintenance of "sacred" zones that allow biodiversity to regenerate autonomously.

However, as the delta faces the dual threats of accelerated sea-level rise and increasing cyclonic frequency, these traditional systems are being pushed to their limits. This study utilizes qualitative analysis and geographical observation to argue that TEK is not a static relic but a dynamic tool for climate adaptation. By integrating indigenous observations of salinity ingress and floral phenology with contemporary geospatial data, more resilient conservation strategies can be formulated. Ultimately, this paper highlights that the sustainability of the Sundarbans depends on bridging the gap between scientific management and the local wisdom of those who have co-evolved with this shifting landscape.

Keywords: *Traditional Ecological Knowledge; Sundarbans, Indigenous Practices; Biocultural Diversity; Mangrove Conservation; Climate Resilience.*

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Recent Hydro-biological changes in Chilika Lagoon, Odisha

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ABSTRACT

Chilika lagoon is the largest lagoon in India facing problems from Hydro-biological changes in last few decades. Hydro-biological changes of Chilika Lagoon have included significant decreases in salinity, leading to the proliferation of invasive freshwater weeds, reduced biodiversity, and depleted fisheries. Siltation from rivers and a partially choked mouth worsened these issues. However, opening a new inlet in 2000 led to a significant increase in salinity, reduced siltation, and a recovery in fish stocks, though the inlet later became choked, causing further hydro-biological shifts. Artificial or natural opening of the Chilika spit also minimize the adverse hydro-biological effects. This paper discusses how various hydro-biological changes have impacted the ecosystem of Chilika Lagoon.

Keywords: *Chilika, Lagoon, Hydro-biology, Salinity, Weeds*

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**LULC dynamics, Wetland Health, and Ecosystem Service Performance: Empirical
Evidence from the Lower Gangetic Plain Wetlands, India**

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands of the Lower Gangetic Plain are ecologically sensitive ecosystems that provide crucial ecosystem services and livelihood support, yet they are significantly threatened by long-term land use and land cover (LULC) dynamics. Although various studies document wetland dynamics, integrated assessments linking spatio-temporal LULC changes, ecological health trajectories, and community-level importance performance remain limited. This research study presents a holistic assessment of wetland changes across the five floodplain wetlands during the period 1995–2025 using a multi-method approach. Multi-temporal satellite imagery was analysed at decadal intervals to quantify LULC changes using supervised classification and GIS-based techniques. LULC-derived indicators were subsequently incorporated into a Wetland Health Trajectory Model (WHTM) to evaluate ecological condition and to classify wetlands into distinct health categories. To capture the human dimension, primary data were collected through structured household surveys (n = 250), and an Importance–Performance (IP) analysis was applied to assess community dependency on various ecosystem services. The results highlights pronounced spatial and temporal heterogeneity in wetland dynamics. All references wetlands (Ahiran, Bishnupur, Chaltia, Belun and Damas) experienced varying degrees of LULC modification, particularly characterized by built-up expansion, agricultural development and a corresponding decline in water bodies and aquatic vegetation also. WHTM evaluation highlights divergent health trajectories, with Ahiran and Bishnupur wetlands exhibiting moderately healthy to degrading or collapsing conditions, while Chaltia, Belun and Damas wetlands indicates vulnerable to degrading or collapsing trends over time. The IP analysis reveals strong community reliance on provisioning services such as fish, water, and aquatic resources, with several services identified as high importance but comparatively low performance for all references wetlands. Overall, the findings indicates that LULC changes exert a substantial influence on wetland health and ecosystem service delivery. The study emphasizes the necessity of integrated, community-based management strategies to enhance wetland resilience and long-term sustainability in the Lower Gangetic Plain.

Keywords: *Wetlands, LULC dynamics; Wetland health; Importance–Performance analysis; Lower Gangetic Plain*

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**Role of Hydrological Parameters in Changing Climate on Wetland Scenario in the
Gangetic Floodplains of West Bengal**

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ABSTRACT

The habitat of floodplain wetlands largely depends on the interplay between rivers and the nearby geomorphological conditions. The purpose of the current study was to ascertain how the HGM conditions are evolving under changing climatic conditions and what the future holds for floodplain wetlands. The case study was conducted along the Diara region of Malda district, an active floodplain that experiences frequent channel migration and floods. A few well-known remote sensing indices, such as the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) and Water Presence Frequency (WPF), along with Brinson's Hydro-Geomorphic (HGM) classification method, have been adopted. The changing landscape ecological scenario was assessed using FRAGSTAT and Google Earth Engine. Important hydro-climatic parameters such as temperature, rainfall, evapotranspiration (ET), groundwater storage, and land surface temperature (LST) were estimated to show the trend of hydro-climatic scenarios using the Mann-Kendall Trend statistic (MK Test) and Innovative Trend Analysis (ITA). The results showed a significantly decreasing trend in the groundwater storage level at a rate of 0.592 kg/m²/year and a significantly increasing trend of ET at a rate of 0.13 mm/year. The study also found a significant reduction in the wetland water area, whereas the Chl-a concentration trend in the wetlands was increasing. The carbon stock also shows a significant change in this region. This is quite alarming for the floodplain wetland ecosystem in the region. According to the HGM stability analysis, only 10% of the wetlands are highly stable, while approximately 16–24% are on the verge of extinction.

Keywords: *Wetlands, Diara Region; Hydro-Geomorphology; Climate Change; Google Earth Engine; Chl-a.*

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Wetland restoration pathways for recovery of wetland health in lower Gangetic flood plains of West Bengal, India

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ABSTRACT

The status of wetlands health has directly affects their functionality. It is crucial to understand these processes in order to develop effective wetland restoration plans, which can create new opportunities for livelihoods while addressing socio-economic and ecological issues. As part of our current research, we have assessed the health of selected wetlands and proposed appropriate restoration strategies for the Murshidabad district, focusing on the lower Gangetic plain of West Bengal. Our approach to evaluating wetland health involved using a habitat-landscape-service model and the analytical hierarchy method. The habitat -landscape-service model used twenty indicator layer and these layers have processed based on primary and secondary data. The results revealed that the wetland health index scores range from 0.16 to 0.85. Notably, Char Sujapur, Balagachi Beel, and Sheel Lake were classified as healthy or very healthy, with index scores exceeding 0.61. In contrast, Bishnupur, Chaltiya, and Belun Beels were found to be in poor condition, with index scores below 0.2. Our assessment identified that active river connections and continuous exchange of water helps for fanual diversity and supports ecosystem services. Furthermore, we have proposed four conservation scenarios to restore the health of sick or unhealthy wetlands to benefiting society.

Keywords: *Lower Gangtoc Floodplain; Wetlands health; Habitat – landscape – service model; Wetland restoration pathways*

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**Assessment of Water Quality and Ecological Status of Bishnupur's Heritage Earthen
Dams, West Bengal, India**

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ABSTRACT

Freshwater resources are increasingly threatened by rapid urbanization, necessitating systematic assessments to ensure their ecological integrity and sustainable use. This study evaluates the water quality and ecological health of seven historic earthen dams in Bishnupur—Jamuna Bandh, Kalindi Bandh, Gantait Bandh, Poka Bandh, Krishna Bandh, Shyam Bandh, and Lal Bandh—constructed during the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries under the Malla dynasty. A total of thirty-five surface water samples were collected, and zooplankton samples were obtained using a 0.5 mm mesh net. The zooplankton assemblage was dominated by Copepoda, Ostracoda, and Protozoa, reflecting variations in ecological conditions among the dams. Surface water samples were analyzed for key physicochemical parameters, including pH, total dissolved solids (TDS), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), dissolved oxygen (DO), electrical conductivity (EC), turbidity, total chlorophyll-a, and total phosphorus (TP). In addition, concentrations of heavy metals (Fe, Zn, Cd, Pb, Ni, and Cr) and major ions (Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , and NO_3^-) were quantified. The Water Quality Index (WQI) was employed to evaluate overall water quality, while multivariate statistical techniques Cluster Analysis (CA) and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) were applied to identify spatial patterns and potential pollution sources. The WQI results classified the majority of the dams as having poor to very poor water quality, with trophic states ranging from mesotrophic to eutrophic. The findings highlight the growing influence of anthropogenic activities on these historic water bodies and emphasize the need for continuous monitoring and targeted management interventions to mitigate pollution and preserve their ecological health.

Keywords: *Water quality assessment; Zooplankton; WQI; Heavy Metal Index; Trophic Status Index.*

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Integrated Evaluation of Water Quality, Heavy Metal Pollution, and Potential Human Health Risks in Dam Reservoirs of the Damodar Valley Corporation (DVC), Eastern India

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ABSTRACT

Rapid industrialization, urban growth, and intensified agricultural practices in eastern India have imposed increasing stress on freshwater systems, particularly dam reservoirs that are vital for drinking water, irrigation, and fisheries. This study presents an integrated evaluation of water quality, heavy metal contamination, and potential human health risks in selected five dam reservoirs of the Damodar Valley Corporation (DVC), Eastern India. Seasonal surface water samples were collected from multiple locations and analyzed for key physicochemical parameters and dissolved heavy metals (Fe, Mn, Cu, Zn, Pb, Cd, Cr, and Ni) using standard methods. Water quality indices, pollution indices, and multivariate statistical techniques were applied to assess contamination levels and identify potential sources. Human health risks were evaluated following United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) guidelines, considering ingestion and dermal exposure pathways. The findings reveal substantial spatial and seasonal variations in water quality, with elevated concentrations of Pb, Cd, and Cr at several sites exceeding permissible limits set by the World Health Organization (WHO) and Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS). Pollution indices indicate moderate to high contamination, largely driven by industrial discharges, coal mining activities, urban runoff, and agricultural inputs. Health risk assessment shows that non-carcinogenic hazard indices for children exceed acceptable thresholds at certain locations, indicating increased vulnerability, while carcinogenic risks associated with Cr and Cd remain within or slightly above recommended limits. Overall, the results highlight emerging water quality deterioration and growing public health concerns in DVC reservoirs. The integrated assessment framework provides valuable insights for effective water resource management, pollution control strategies, and sustainable watershed planning to protect ecosystem health and human well-being.

Keywords: *Heavy metal contamination; Water quality indices; Seasonal variability; Ecological risk assessment; Damodar Valley Corporation*

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**Hydrological Dynamics and Socio-Economic Implications of Wetlands in Labpur Block,
Birbhum District**

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands are important hydrological and ecological landscape units that function as transitional zones between land and water systems while supporting local livelihoods. In recent decades, increasing anthropogenic pressure has led to the rapid degradation of wetlands across India. The present study analyses the hydrological behaviour and socio-economic impact of wetlands in Labpur Block of Birbhum District, West Bengal, with special emphasis on seasonal variation, morphological change, flood regulation, and livelihood dependency.

The research is based on primary and secondary data, collected through multi-season field surveys, household questionnaires, soil and sediment sampling, bathymetric measurements, and hydrological observations, supported by satellite imagery, topographical maps, census records, and institutional data. Spatio-temporal techniques were applied to assess changes in wetland extent, depth, deposition patterns, drainage morphometry, groundwater interaction, and flood characteristics.

The results indicate that wetland hydrology in the study area is strongly controlled by rainfall variability, river discharge, drainage characteristics, and groundwater flow. Declining monsoonal rainfall, increasing sedimentation, and reduced water-holding capacity have intensified flood stagnation and contributed to wetland shrinkage. Human interventions such as wetland conversion for agriculture, embankment and road construction, excessive groundwater extraction, and mini-barrage development have further disrupted natural hydrological processes.

These changes have significantly influenced agricultural practices, fishing activities, settlement patterns, and occupational structure, increasing economic vulnerability among wetland-dependent communities. The study emphasizes the need for integrated wetland management, incorporating ecological conservation, sustainable resource use, and community participation. The proposed management strategies aim to restore hydrological balance, enhance livelihood security, and ensure long-term sustainability of floodplain wetlands. The findings provide a useful framework for wetland conservation planning in similar regions of eastern India.

Keywords: *Wetland hydrology; Flood regulation; Socio-economic impacts; Livelihood dependency; Land-use change*

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Monitoring Brick Kiln Expansion and Riverine Ecosystem Disturbance in Howrah and North 24 Parganas: A Google Earth Engine–Based Geospatial Assessment

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ABSTRACT

The high rate of growth of the brick kilns, both in the peri-urban and rural environments, has increasingly become a major cause of environmental pressure, especially to the riverine environments. This paper investigates the spatial growth of the brick kilns and the resultant disrupters of riverine ecosystems in the Howrah and North-24-Parganas districts in West Bengal through the geospatial framework of a Google-Earth-Engine (GEE). The overview analysis of LULC changes with time was done with multi-temporal satellite images of the Landsat and Sentinel missions. Spectral indices were used to apply supervised classification techniques that were used to determine the locations of the brick kiln and gauge the alterations of vegetation cover, surface water and changes of floodplain properties. A buffer and proximity analysis was carried out to determine the spatial relationship of the clusters of brick kiln and the major river systems. The findings show that the density of the brick kilns has significantly risen in the two districts with a significant concentration on the banks of rivers and the floodplains. This expansion is associated with apparent declines in the riparian vegetation, land surface modification, and riverine landscape fragmentation. Regions that are found to be nearer to the kiln clusters have greater rates of ecosystem disruption than those that are not. The results underscore the ecological hazard posed by uncontrolled brick kiln development and show the necessity to improve land-use planning, regulatory enforcement, and the implementation of the sustainable process of producing bricks to mitigate the ecological risks of riverine ecosystems of fast-paced urbanization areas.

Keywords: *Brick kilns; Riverine ecosystem; Land use/land cover change; Riparian vegetation.*

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**A Synergistic Approach to Aquaculture Pond Extraction Using Sentinel Imagery
Through Spatial Metrics and Machine Learning Techniques**

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ABSTRACT

Aquaculture plays a vital role in global food systems by meeting the growing demand for aquatic protein while reducing pressure on wild fish stocks. In India, traditional practices such as mud ponds, tank-based systems, and paddy-cum-fish farming remain crucial for sustaining rural livelihoods and food security. These traditional systems rely on local knowledge and natural processes, making them environmentally friendly and suitable for long-term aquaculture development. In this context, the present study aims to improve aquaculture land classification by integrating GLCM (Grey-Level Co-occurrence Matrix) based texture features with spectral indices and four advanced supervised classification techniques Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), and Classification and Regression Trees (CART) were employed, to evaluate their applicability in the Keleghai and Haldi riverside blocks of Purba Medinipur district for sustainable resource management. GLCM analyzes the spatial relationships between pairs of pixels in grayscale images to extract texture features such as contrast, correlation, homogeneity, entropy, and angular second moment, which help describe spatial patterns. This study used Sentinel-1 SAR (VV+VH) and Sentinel-2A multispectral data of 2024, processed in the Google Earth Engine platform. Ground-truth GPS points and Google Earth Pro validation polygons supported supervised classification. Patch-based geometric features (area, perimeter, compactness, extent ratio, and shape index) were analyzed to distinguish aquaculture ponds from other land uses. A Seasonal Water Sensitivity Index (SWSI), derived from median GLCM texture features, was developed to separate aquaculture ponds from seasonal water bodies such as rice fields and dry abandoned aquaculture farms. The integrated use of spectral, textural, and geometric features achieved an overall classification accuracy of 83.5%, demonstrating a strong capability to distinguish aquaculture ponds from other land-use types. The resulting spatial information supports sustainable aquaculture management, improves rural livelihood, and environmental conservation.

Keywords: *Aquaculture, GLCM (Grey-Level Co-occurrence Matrix), texture analysis, SWSI (Seasonal Water Sensitivity Index), machine learning.*

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**Wetland Transformation and Floodplain Dynamics in the Bhagirathi–Hooghly Basin,
Eastern India**

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ABSTRACT

The wetland ecosystems of the Bhagirathi–Hooghly floodplain in eastern India represent a dynamic interface between fluvial processes, monsoonal hydrology, and human land use. Historically, this floodplain supported a mosaic of natural wetlands, oxbow lakes, marshes, and seasonally inundated flood basins. These wetlands sustained high levels of biodiversity and provided essential ecosystem services, including nutrient cycling, groundwater recharge, fisheries, and flood attenuation. Over recent decades, the structure and function of these wetland systems have been profoundly altered by a combination of anthropogenic pressures and climatic variability. Expansion of agriculture, urbanization, channel modification through dredging and embankment construction, and pollution from industrial and domestic sources have fragmented wetland habitats and disrupted natural hydrological connectivity. Concurrently, changes in flood regimes have modified patterns of inundation crucial for wetland productivity. These transformations have led to declines in native flora and fauna, reduced carbon sequestration potential, and heightened vulnerability to flood for local communities dependent on wetland resources. This study analyses recent ecological, hydrological, and socio-economic consequences of wetland change on the Bhagirathi–Hooghly floodplain. It highlights the urgent need for integrated management strategies that balance developmental needs with wetland conservation, promote sustainable livelihoods, and enhance the resilience of floodplain ecosystems under future environmental change.

Keywords: *Bhagirathi–Hooghly floodplain; wetland ecosystems; changes in flood regimes; oxbow lakes; resilience of floodplain ecosystems.*

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**Urban Wetlands in Socio-Ecological Complex Systems: Cultural Ecosystem Service
Contributions to Livable City Development**

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ABSTRACT

Urban wetlands represent critical components of socio-ecological complex systems, providing diverse cultural ecosystem services that enhance urban livability and human well-being. This study examines the contribution of urban wetlands to cultural ecosystem services, including recreational opportunities, aesthetic value, cultural identity, educational functions, and psychological benefits within rapidly urbanizing environments. The research adopts an integrated socio-economic–ecological framework to evaluate the interactions between human activities, environmental processes, and wetland ecosystem functions. Using geospatial analysis, field-based observations, and socio-economic assessment, the study investigates the spatial distribution, accessibility, and community perception of cultural ecosystem services derived from urban wetlands. The findings highlight that urban wetlands significantly support social cohesion, environmental awareness, and urban quality of life, while also contributing to ecological balance. However, increasing urban expansion, land-use transformation, and inadequate policy integration threaten the sustainability of these services. The study emphasizes the importance of incorporating urban wetlands into sustainable city planning, ecosystem-based management strategies, and participatory governance frameworks to strengthen cultural ecosystem service delivery and promote resilient and livable urban development.

Keywords: *Urban wetlands; Socio-ecological systems; Urban livability; Ecosystem-based management; Community perception; Urban resilience.*

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Wetlands as Blue Carbon Ecosystems and Climate Change Response

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands are highly valued ecosystems that provide essential ecological and economic services, yet they are increasingly threatened worldwide, particularly by urban encroachment along city fringes. The wetlands of Kolkata illustrate this challenge. Despite being vital to the city's survival, these water bodies remain severely degraded. Their locational uniqueness makes them especially important for environmental purification, with waterlogged urban landscapes and oxygen-producing vegetation contributing significantly to atmospheric oxygen balance. Beyond their local significance, wetlands function as critical blue carbon ecosystems, playing a key role in climate change mitigation and adaptation. Coastal wetlands, including mangroves, salt marshes, and seagrass meadows are highly efficient at capturing and storing atmospheric carbon dioxide. Their high primary productivity and distinctive biogeochemical processes enable long-term carbon sequestration within both biomass and sediments. The Sundarbans, the world's largest contiguous mangrove forest shared by India and Bangladesh, exemplifies the importance of blue carbon ecosystems along the Indian coast. Its extensive tidal wetlands sequester carbon at rates surpassing many terrestrial forests, while also supporting rich biodiversity and providing ecosystem services such as coastal protection and nutrient cycling. Similar coastal wetlands elsewhere along India's coastline enhance regional climate resilience but face mounting threats from sea-level rise, land-use change, and human pressures. These stressors diminish carbon storage capacity and risk transforming wetlands from carbon sinks into greenhouse gas sources. Strengthening conservation and restoration of India's coastal wetlands by integrating blue carbon dynamics into policy frameworks is therefore essential for effective climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies.

Keywords: *Coastal wetlands; blue carbon ecosystems; climate change; carbon sequestration.*

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Socio-economic status and livelihood of fishermen community in Digha Coast of West Bengal, India

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ABSTRACT

Marine fishing is one of the most significant livelihood opportunities for the residents of the Digha Coastal region, and their socioeconomic status is significantly influenced by it. The objective of the current investigation is to evaluate the socioeconomic status of the fishermen Community of Digha Coast. Selected localities in the Digha Coastal region were the source of the data collection. A random sample of 2656 respondents were analysed. In order to ascertain the socioeconomic status of the fishermen community, the questionnaire survey procedure was implemented. Cross-tabulation and percentage analysis were implemented in this investigation. The interpretations that were made during the investigation are the basis for the findings and observations. The outcome indicates that 30% of the 618 families are above the poverty line, while the remaining 70% are below the poverty line, as per the FAO's guidelines. The present investigation will contribute to the creation of novel economic prospects and the expansion of the resource base to impoverished coastal populations.

Keywords: *Socio-economic; Livelihood; Fisherman; Digha Coast.*

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**Geospatial Integration in Agricultural Land Suitability and Crop Production of
Bankura District, West Bengal, India**

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ABSTRACT

The present study analyses the role of geospatial integration in assessing agricultural land suitability in relation to crop production. Agricultural productivity in the region is highly dynamic and influenced by variations in physical, climatic and soil-related parameters. Using geospatial techniques, the study evaluates major environmental factors that determine land suitability. Key datasets include SRTM DEM, Google Earth Pro imagery, Geologic provinces in South Asia (USGS), DSMW (ESRI), Rainfall, Land Surface Temperature (LST) and Relative humidity. Bankura district, located in western West Bengal, exhibits diverse physiographic conditions. Geological structure, drainage pattern, elevation, slope, aspect and soil texture collectively influence agricultural potential. The western part is dominated by Precambrian rocks, while the eastern part is composed of Quaternary sediments. Major rivers such as the Dwarakeshwar, Damodar, Shilabati and Kangsabati show a dendritic pattern with a northwest–southeast flow direction. Soils in the district are mainly loam, sandy loam and sandy clay loam, with local variations in pH, organic carbon and nutrients. Rainfall ranges from 180–200 cm in the south to 140–160 cm in the west, while LST varies between 40°–48°C in summer and 10°–12°C in winter. Crop production was assessed using crop concentration, combination, and diversification and cropping pattern. These indicators were integrated with land-suitability parameters and validated using NDVI, LU/LC and Google Earth Pro imagery. The study finally reveals a strong correlation between land suitability and crop production, confirming that geospatial integration is an effective spatial analytical technique for assessing agricultural potential.

Keywords: *Geospatial Integration; Agricultural Land Suitability; Cropping pattern; Crop Production; Land Surface Temperature.*

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**Role of the Wetlands and Water Bodies in Modulating Land Surface Temperature in the
Kolkata Metropolitan Area**

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzes the cooling effect and spatial impact of urban water-vegetation systems, focusing on the East Kolkata Wetlands in the Kolkata Metropolitan Area. Wetlands function as vital thermal regulators within urban environments due to their high moisture availability, evapotranspiration capacity, and water-vegetation interactions, while also serving as key ecological assets that support hydrological regulation, biodiversity conservation, and ecosystem service provision. The findings indicate that areas dominated by blue-green spaces exhibit significantly lower land surface temperatures (LSTs) than adjacent built-up zones. Proximity-based analysis reveals a mean cooling effect of up to 2.81 °C within a 250 m radius of water-vegetation systems. The East Kolkata Wetlands exhibit a distinct cooling effect, with an average LST reduction of approximately 1.25 °C, underscoring their role as a regional-scale thermal buffer. Surface UHI intensity analysis identifies pronounced warming in densely urbanized cores with limited vegetative cover, where thermal anomalies exceed 6 °C relative to peripheral areas. The Urban Thermal Field Variance Index (UTFVI) further indicates escalating thermal stress in vegetation-deficient zones, reflected by a 21.79% increase in areas classified under the ‘worst’ thermal category. Spatial regression analyses with OLS and GWR reveal moisture- and vegetation-driven cooling effects and intensified heating over impervious surfaces. Validation with ground observations from a Davis Vantage Vue station shows strong agreement with satellite-derived LST ($R^2 = 0.702$). These results underscore the importance of conserving wetlands and integrating urban water-vegetation systems into climate-conscious urban planning to improve thermal comfort and resilience.

Keywords: *Blue-Green Spaces; Wetlands; Land Surface Temperature (LST); Urban Heat Island (UHI); Urban Thermal Field Variance Index (UTFVI)*

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**Urban Growth, Land-Use Dynamics and Wetland Degradation in the Midnapore
Kharagpur Development Authority (MKDA) Region of West Bengal: A Geospatial
Assessment**

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ABSTRACT

Rapid urbanisation has significantly altered land-use patterns in developing regions, often leading to the degradation of ecologically sensitive landscapes such as wetlands. Understanding the dynamics of urban growth and associated land-use changes is therefore essential for sustainable urban planning and environmental conservation. The present study examines the spatio-temporal patterns of urban expansion, land-use dynamics, and wetland degradation in the Midnapore Kharagpur Development Authority (MKDA) region of West Bengal using a geospatial approach. Multi-temporal Landsat satellite imagery for the years 2001, 2011, and 2021, along with projections for 2031, were analysed using ArcGIS and QGIS to generate land-use/land-cover maps and quantify changes over time. The results reveal a substantial increase in built-up areas from 14.42% in 2001 to 32% in 2021, with projections indicating further expansion to 42.98% by 2031. Conversely, vegetation and wetland areas experienced significant decline, with green cover decreasing from 21.19% in 2001 to 9.64% in 2021 and expected to fall to 6.78% by 2031, reflecting growing ecological stress. The Average Annual Urban Expansion Rate (AUER) of 6.08% during 2001–2021 highlights the intensity of urban transformation in the region. Concentric Buffer Ring analysis indicates that urban growth was initially concentrated in the inner zones (CBR-1 and CBR-2), driven by infill development and densification, before gradually extending towards peripheral areas, resulting in increased pressure on wetlands and other open spaces. The findings underscore the strong link between uncontrolled urban growth, land-use transitions, and wetland degradation in the MKDA region. The study emphasises the need for integrated land-use planning strategies that prioritise wetland conservation, urban ecosystem restoration, and sustainable green space management to enhance ecological resilience and support long-term sustainable urban development.

Keywords: *Urban Growth; Land-Use Dynamics; Wetland Degradation; MKDA; Geospatial Analysis; Sustainable Urban Development.*

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Land-Use Change, Urbanization and Wetland Degradation in Delhi-NCT

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ABSTRACT

Urbanization in the National Capital Territory (NCT) of Delhi has resulted in massive land-use and land-cover (LULC) alteration in the past decades, which has significant impacts on wetland ecosystems. In recent context, these are critical in hydrological regulation, biodiversity provision, and climate regulation. This study examines the spatio-temporal LULC change of the city of Delhi-NCT as well as assessing its effects on wetland degradation through multi-temporal satellite images, spatial measures in GIS, and landscape fragmentation measures. Findings show that the area of built-up areas has grown significantly at the cost of agricultural land, floodplains, and open spaces and the large wetlands. Wetlands including the Yamuna floodplain, Najafgarh Jheel, and Sanjay Lake have been shrinking and encroaching. Natural drainage networks, groundwater recharge, and urban heat island effects and flood risks have been disturbed by the extent of converting permeable surfaces into impervious cover. The statistical analysis shows significant relationships between the trends of urban growth and the deteriorating ecological integrity and wetlands. Moreover, there are policy gaps, laxity on the regulations, and conflicting land-use interests that have contributed to the degradation of ecosystems. This paper proposes combined, evidence-based urban planning constructs, which incorporate wetland protection, buffer zoning, and ecological restoration in New Delhi development agenda. This is vital in incorporating wetlands into the urban resilience plans to promote the survival of ecosystem services, reduce climate risks, and maintain long-term environmental sustainability in the fast-growing megacities.

Keywords: *Delhi-NCT; Land-use/land-cover change (LULC); Urbanization; Wetland degradation; Wetland management; Sustainable urban planning*

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**Monitoring Urban-Induced Wetland Degradation in Kolkata City: A Remote Sensing–
Based Analysis**

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands in rapidly urbanizing cities are under increasing pressure due to land-use transformation, infrastructure expansion, and population growth. Kolkata City, historically characterized by extensive wetland systems, has experienced significant ecological stress over recent decades. This study aims to monitor and quantify urban-induced wetland degradation in Kolkata City using remote sensing and geospatial techniques. Multi-temporal satellite imagery was analyzed to assess changes in wetland extent and surrounding land-use patterns over selected time periods. Standard image preprocessing, supervised classification, and change detection techniques were employed to delineate wetlands and urban built-up areas. Accuracy assessment was conducted using ground truth data and high-resolution reference imagery. The results reveal a substantial decline in wetland area, accompanied by a marked increase in built-up land, indicating a strong spatial correlation between urban expansion and wetland loss. Fragmentation and encroachment of wetlands were most pronounced in peri-urban zones, where unplanned development and infrastructure growth are dominant. The findings highlight the role of rapid urbanization as a key driver of wetland degradation, leading to reduced ecosystem services such as flood regulation, biodiversity support, and micro-climatic moderation. This study demonstrates the effectiveness of remote sensing as a cost-efficient and reliable tool for long-term monitoring of urban wetland dynamics. The outcomes provide valuable insights for urban planners and policymakers, emphasizing the need for integrated land-use planning and stronger wetland conservation strategies to ensure sustainable urban development in Kolkata City.

Keywords: *Urbanization; Wetland Degradation; Ecological Stress; Urban Wetland Dynamics; Urban Expansion*

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A study on Fishfaunal Diversity of Tamal River

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ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted from May 2024 to April 2025 to assess the ichthyofaunal diversity of the Tamal River in Paschim Medinipur district, West Bengal, India. Findings indicate the presence of 58 indigenous fish species, classified under 23 families across 8 orders, with Perciformes exhibiting the highest diversity (8 families, 20 species). The Cyprinidae family is the most dominant, representing 27.59% of the recorded species. Notably, *Gagatacania* (Hamilton, 1822) was documented for the first time in Paschim Medinipur district. Among the fish species identified in the Tamal River, 39.66% are utilized as food fish, 1.72% serve ornamental purposes, and 58.62% fulfil both roles. Consequently, most fish species possess significant socio-economic value for the communities adjacent to the Tamal River. The calculated Shannon-Weaver index (H) ranged from 3.58 to 3.79, while the Simpson's index (D) ranged from 0.023 to 0.032 across sampling sites, indicating substantial fish diversity within the river. Species evenness results suggest that individual species are approaching disturbed conditions in the Tamal River ecosystem. According to IUCN version 2024.1 classifications, 75.86% of species are categorized as Least Concern, 3.45% as Vulnerable, 8.62% as Near Threatened, 10.34% as Not Evaluated, and 1.72% as Data Deficient. At the local level, 71.42% of species are considered at risk and require urgent conservation actions to prevent extinction. Thus, this study provides essential documentation of macrofaunal diversity in the Tamal River, serving as a valuable resource for future researchers, policy planners, and for the formulation of effective conservation and management strategies for the region's fish diversity.

Keywords: *Ichthyofaunal diversity; Fish community structure; Conservation status; Socio-economic importance; Tamal River*

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Fish-Eating Bird Diversity in Purba Medinipur, West Bengal, India

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ABSTRACT

Fish-eating birds play a vital role in wetland ecosystems and serve as useful indicators of aquatic habitat health. Both natural and modified coastal wetlands are home to many bird species, but these habitats face growing human impact. This study reports on the variety and conservation status of fish-eating birds in Purba Medinipur, West Bengal, India, drawing on systematic observations from June 2024 through May 2025. Researchers identified ten species of fish-eating birds, spanning seven orders and eight families, highlighting the ecological diversity and significance of the area's wetland and coastal habitats. Despite their ecological significance, fish-eating birds in the study area are experiencing mounting threats from rapid urbanization, habitat conversion, unregulated tourism, and climate-change-driven stressors such as sea-level rise and reduced prey availability. Although most recorded species are currently classified as Least Concern by the IUCN, continued habitat degradation may lead to population declines in the absence of effective management. The findings underscore the need for long-term monitoring, habitat protection, and community-inclusive conservation strategies to safeguard fish-eating avifauna and maintain coastal wetland biodiversity in Purba Medinipur.

Keywords: *Fish-eating birds; Coastal wetlands; Avifauna diversity; Conservation biology*

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Induced Breeding of Small Indigenous Ornamental Fish *Pethia conchonius* (Hamilton, 1822) in Captive Conditions

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ABSTRACT

Pethia conchonius (Hamilton, 1822) is an important small indigenous fish with food and ornamental values. It belongs to the family Cyprinidae and is found in India, Afghanistan, Pakistan, Nepal, Bangladesh, and Myanmar. Species have gradually decreased in India due to the culture of Indian Major Carp and selective exotic species. The present study aims to make dose selection for induced breeding, embryonic, and larval development of *P. conchonius* for conservation and livelihood for people. The optimum dose was selected through trial and error method by applying five doses (0.5 ml/kg, 1 ml/kg, 1.5 ml/kg, 2 ml/kg, 2.5 ml/kg body weight) of synthetic hormone (ovotide) to both sexes. The study reveals that single dose effective for both male and female as well as the optimum dose of synthetic hormone ovotide @ 1.5 ml/kg body weight is effective for induced breeding of *P. conchonius*. At the optimum dose, fertilisation and hatching rates were $82.93 \pm 0.79\%$ and $77.4 \pm 0.66\%$, respectively. The results of the present study will help make *P. conchonius* a better ornamental plan for local people to generate income and protect from nature.

Keywords: *Induced Breeding; Conservation; Optimum dos; Pethia conchonius*

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Wetlands Act as Nature's Kidneys

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands, which include marshes, swamps, bogs, and estuaries, are places where water covers the soil or is present close to the surface, creating a unique ecosystem that transitions between land and water. These areas support specialized plants and animals by filtering water, controlling floods, and providing essential habitats. Although definitions vary slightly, they all reflect the ecosystem's water-saturated, biologically rich nature. By eliminating contaminants, silt, and waste nutrients before they reach bigger bodies of water, they act as a natural filtration system, purifying water. Similar to how human kidneys filter waste from the blood, wetlands serve a number of vital environmental cleaning purposes. When water enters a wetland, its flow slows down, allowing silt, soil, and organic materials to settle at the bottom; plants and microorganisms break down or absorb excess nutrients like nitrogen and phosphorus, which are frequently from agricultural runoff, preventing harmful algal blooms downstream; microbes in waterlogged, oxygen-poor soils can transform pollutants, including heavy metals; and wetland plant roots can bind and remove up to 90% of sediments from runoff. Wetlands support approximately 40% of all plant and animal species, provide vital nurseries for fish and habitats for migratory birds, hold water, and allow it to slowly seep into the ground, replenishing aquifers used for drinking and irrigation. In addition to filtering water, wetlands also provide a variety of ecosystem services that maintain the health of the planet, absorb heavy rainfall and release it gradually, and act as a natural buffer against floods and storms. Despite making up only 6% of the Earth's surface, wetlands store nearly 30% of land-based carbon, making them crucial for mitigating climate change. Wetlands are disappearing three times more quickly than forests, despite their significance. Urbanization, the growth of agriculture, and pollution are the main challenges. World Wetlands Day is observed annually on February 2 to increase awareness of the Ramsar Convention, the main international agreement devoted to their protection. Therefore, efforts to create, preserve, or restore wetlands and the ecosystem services they offer—which are crucial for maintaining biodiversity, enhancing water quality, and reducing flooding—are necessary for wetland conservation.

Keywords: *Wetland ecosystem services; Natural water filtration; Flood regulation; Biodiversity conservation; Climate change mitigation*

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From Aquatic Ecosystem to Human Health: A Zooplankton-Based Multimetric Study

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ABSTRACT

Freshwater ecosystems are increasingly threatened by anthropogenic activities that degrade water quality, disrupt biological communities, and pose potential risks to human health. Zooplankton, due to their rapid response to environmental stressors, serve as effective bioindicators of ecological condition. The present study examines the relationship between hydrobiological parameters, zooplankton assemblages, and associated human health risks in selected freshwater habitats. A total of forty-eight water samples were collected year-round from ponds, canals, and waterlogged areas. Physicochemical parameters and concentrations of seven heavy metals were analyzed. Zooplankton were identified and quantified, and multivariate statistical techniques, pollution indices, and the Water Quality Index (WQI) were employed to assess ecological status. Human health risks were evaluated using hazard quotient (HQ) and hazard index (HI) models. The study recorded 72 zooplankton species, with Copepoda dominating the assemblage (51.39%), followed by Rotifera (34.72%) and Cladocera (13.89%). Concentrations of Hg, Cd, and Ni frequently exceeded permissible limits set by BIS and WHO. The Metal Index and Nemerow Pollution Index indicated contamination in 83.34% and 97.92% of the samples, respectively, while WQI classified 47.92% of sampling sites as unsuitable for drinking purposes. Significant negative correlations ($P < 0.05$) were observed between heavy metal concentrations and zooplankton abundance. Nickel and zinc posed the highest non-carcinogenic health risks, particularly for children. The findings highlight the strong influence of industrial discharge, agricultural runoff, and urban inputs on water quality and zooplankton community structure, reinforcing the role of zooplankton as sensitive bioindicators. The study emphasizes the urgent need for integrated pollution control, continuous monitoring, and sustainable management strategies to protect freshwater ecosystems and safeguard human health.

Keywords: *Anthropogenic contamination; Ecological risk assessment; Heavy metals; Human health risk; Pollution indices; Zooplankton diversity.*

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Microplastic Pollution in Freshwater Ecosystems: Insights from Commercial Bivalves of Undivided Medinipur District

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ABSTRACT

Aquatic ecosystems are increasingly degraded by anthropogenic pollution, one of them is microplastic (MPs) emerging as a prevalent and persistent contaminant affecting freshwater biodiversity and ecosystem services. Bivalves, due to their filter-feeding behaviour, ecological importance and socioeconomic value for rural communities, serve as effective bioindicators of aquatic environmental health. The present study assesses the concentration and distribution of MPs in commercially important freshwater bivalve species collected from East Medinipur, West Medinipur and Jhargram district of West Bengal, India, regions where inland fisheries contribute significantly to local livelihoods and food security. A total of 150 bivalve specimens were collected from local markets for analysis. The selected bivalves had body weight ranging from approximately 24g to 58g and lengths between 4.5 cm and 8 cm. From 720.6 g of dissected tissue (including gut and muscle), 1027 MP particles were isolated, creating an average of 1.42 MP particles per gram of tissue. The MPs were categorized by colour- predominantly red, followed by black, blue, green and white and also by morphology, including fibres, fragments and sheets. Visual identification under stereomicroscope and polymer characterization via Raman micro spectroscopy indicated that the highest MP abundance occurred in bivalves collected from Jhargram district, while the lowest levels were recorded in those from East Medinipur district. The findings highlight the extent of plastic pollution in waterbodies, potential to compromise bivalve biodiversity and the sustainability of rural livelihood dependent on these resources.

Keywords: *Freshwater bivalves; Filter-feeding; Microplastic; Rural livelihood; Raman Spectroscopy.*

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Sustainable Aquafeed Development including *Moringa oleifera* Leaf Meal: Effects on Growth Performance and Haematological Responses of *Labeo bata*.

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ABSTRACT

The growing expansion of aquaculture has produced a pressing need for economical, nutritionally balanced feeds, especially for *Labeo bata*, one of the most widely cultivated fish species globally. Fishmeal, the traditional protein source, is costly and unsustainable. *Moringa oleifera*, often called the “miracle tree,” presents a promising alternative thanks to its high levels of protein, vitamins, and minerals. The present study evaluated the growth performance and haematological parameters of *Labeo bata* over 60 days by substituting varying ratios of *M. oleifera* leaves for fish meal (FM). Five distinct dietary groups were established using a basal diet supplemented with varied proportions of *M. oleifera* leaf meal, substituting T1 (0% MOL), T2 (25% MOL), T3 (50% MOL), T4 (75% MOL), and T5 (100% MOL) for the FM component of the diets. The findings revealed significant differences in growth parameters, with the fish fed the T4 (75% MOL) diet showing, in comparison to the other diets, the highest final weight and specific growth rate. Fish fed D4 diets had significantly increased mean values for both red blood cells and white blood cells. In conclusion, the aquafeed industry may use MOL in place of 75% FM to improve *Labeo bata* growth and health. It can also improve fish's ability to withstand adverse environmental conditions and improve their haematological function.

Keywords: *Fish meal; Moringa leaf; Growth performance; Health status*

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**Cultural Practices and Microbial Water Quality at Selected Hooghly River Ghats within
a Riverine Wetland System in Kolkata, India**

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ABSTRACT

The Hooghly River functions as a vital riverine wetland system in Kolkata, supporting a wide range of cultural ecosystem services, including ferry transportation, ritual bathing, and large-scale religious gatherings. However, intensive human–river interactions at urban ghats have raised serious concerns regarding microbial contamination and associated public health risks, particularly during the monsoon season. The present study assessed the microbial and physicochemical water quality of selected Hooghly River ghats representing distinct patterns of cultural use. Four sites—Howrah Station Ferry Ghat (transport and daily use), Babu Ghat (ritual bathing), Panihati Mahatsabtala Ghat (mass cultural gatherings), and Serampore Ferry Ghat (mixed residential and transport activities)—were selected to capture spatial variability in anthropogenic pressure. Water samples were collected during the monsoon season of 2025 and analyzed for key physicochemical parameters, including biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), dissolved oxygen (DO), turbidity, and ammonia, along with microbial indicators such as Total Coliform and Fecal Coliform. To evaluate microbial exposure risk, a Microbial Risk Index (MRI) was calculated based on coliform concentrations, while a simplified Water Quality Index (WQI) was used to assess the overall water quality status using selected physicochemical parameters. The results revealed elevated microbial contamination at all selected ghats, with the highest MRI values recorded at transport-dominated and residentially influenced locations. The simplified WQI classification indicated generally poor water quality conditions during the monsoon, largely driven by increased organic loading, high turbidity, and nutrient enrichment. Overall, the study highlights the influence of cultural practices and anthropogenic pressure on microbial water quality within the Hooghly Riverine Wetland System and underscores the need for improved monitoring, sanitation measures, and management strategies to mitigate public health risks at culturally significant riverfronts.

Keywords: *Hooghly River; Riverine Wetland; Cultural Ghats; Microbial Water Quality; Microbial Risk Index (MRI); Water Quality Index (WQI); Monsoon Season; Public Health Risk*

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Evaluating the Impact of Climate Variability on the Mangrove Ecosystem of the Sundarbans

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ABSTRACT

Mangrove ecosystems are highly productive and climate-sensitive coastal habitats that provide essential services, including biodiversity conservation, shoreline stabilization, and carbon sequestration. The Sundarbans, a significant UNESCO World Heritage Site, is the world's largest contiguous mangrove forest and plays a crucial role in wetland tourism in India. However, rising temperatures, uncertain precipitation patterns, climate variability, and increasing anthropogenic activities threaten the long-term stability of this vital ecosystem. This study analyzes historical mangrove vegetation dynamics in the Indian Sundarbans from 1986 to 2024 and projects future vegetation conditions over the next 12 years, up to 2036. We employ an integrated framework that combines climate models from CMIP6 and remote sensing data derived from satellites. Vegetation health was assessed using Landsat-derived time series data analyzed through the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI), along with the Mann-Kendall test for trend analysis. Climate variables, such as temperature and precipitation, were sourced from the bias-corrected CMIP6 ACCESS-CM2 model under two emission scenarios: SSP4.5 (moderate emissions) and SSP8.5 (high emissions). Validation against ERA5 and CHIRPS datasets showed a strong correlation for temperature ($R = 0.94$) and moderate correlation for precipitation ($R = 0.48$). Additionally, atmospheric pollutants (SO_2 , CO , CH_2 , O_2 , and Aerosol Absorbing Index) from Sentinel-5P data (2018–2024) were examined. Correlation analyses revealed significant negative relationships between climatic variables and air pollutants. Multi-regression projections indicate moderate increases in vegetation indices under both scenarios; however, SSP8.5 presents greater climatic stress and seasonal fluctuations, while SSP4.5 suggests more stable vegetation conditions. These results underscore the combined impact of climate variability and air pollution on mangrove resilience, supporting SSP4.5 as a preferable pathway for long-term conservation and climate adaptation planning.

Keywords: *Mangrove vegetation dynamics; NDVI; EVI; CMIP6; Remote Sensing; Vegetation Prediction.*

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**Feeding Behavior Analysis and Gastro-somatic Index (Gasi) during different phases of
Breeding Cycle of *Mystustengara* (Hamilton, 1822) from West Bengal, India**

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ABSTRACT

Mystustengara is a small indigenous freshwater fish species and have nutritional value and also have good market demand. For fulfillment of market demand the species are collected from natural source. In order to decline natural population, suppliers cannot meet market demand so breeding and large-scale seed production of *M. tengara* are needed. Therefore, a study has been conducted to gain knowledge on food and feeding habits of species which help profitably culture practices of species in captivity. In this period, we studied feeding intensity, Gastro-somatic index (GaSI), Relative length of gut (RLG). From our observation small fish, crustaceans and zooplankton (rotifer) are most preferred food item in gut of this species. GaSI value 2.50 for immature, 3.89 for maturing phases, 3.52 for mature phases, 2.83 for spent phases was recorded in breeding season. GaSI value was lowest in immature phases and very high at maturing phases. Lowest GaSI value indicate the low feeding intensity at winter season but high feeding intensity in maturing phases for development of gonads. According to result of RLG value *M.tengara* consider as carnivore fish.

Keyword: *Feeding intensity; GaSI; RLG; M.tengara*

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**Remote Sensing–Based Assessment of Forest and Wetland Health and Biomass
Dynamics in the Challenging Terrains of Sikkim and Darjeeling**

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ABSTRACT

Forests and associated wetlands in mountainous regions such as Sikkim and Darjeeling form an interconnected ecosystem that plays a critical role in biodiversity conservation, carbon sequestration, hydrological regulation, and climate resilience. However, monitoring forest canopy condition, above-ground biomass (AGB), and wetland–forest dynamics in these complex terrains remains challenging due to rugged topography, frequent cloud cover, climatic variability, and limited field accessibility. This study employs a multi-source remote sensing and GIS-based approach to assess forest and wetland ecosystem health and biomass dynamics across the Sikkim–Darjeeling region over the period 2014–2024. Satellite datasets from Sentinel-2 MSI, Sentinel-1 SAR, MODIS, and CHIRPS rainfall products were integrated to derive a suite of vegetation, structural, chlorophyll, and moisture indices, including NDVI, NDMI, fPAR, GCI, RCI, RVI, and VV/VH ratios. Optical indices were used to evaluate canopy vigor, chlorophyll content, and moisture conditions, while radar-based indices enabled structural assessment of forest cover and wetland vegetation under persistent cloud conditions. Correlation analysis revealed a strong influence of monsoonal rainfall on vegetation greenness and moisture-sensitive indices, highlighting seasonal and interannual variability in both forested and wetland-associated landscapes. Spatial analysis identified pronounced ecological gradients across the region: southern zones exhibited consistently high vegetation and moisture indices due to favorable climatic and hydrological conditions, while northern and central areas showed greater temporal variability linked to elevation, anthropogenic pressure, and rainfall variability. Wetland-adjacent forest patches demonstrated distinct moisture and productivity signatures, underscoring the importance of forest–wetland interactions in regulating ecosystem functioning. The application of Google Earth Engine enabled efficient processing of large, multi-temporal datasets and facilitated long-term change detection. Overall, this study presents a scalable and cost-effective framework for integrated forest and wetland ecosystem monitoring in data-scarce mountainous regions. The findings support informed decision-making for sustainable forest and wetland management, conservation planning, and climate adaptation strategies, while emphasizing the growing role of continuous geospatial monitoring augmented by AI and machine learning techniques.

Keywords: *Canopy density; Above Ground Biomass (AGB); Remote Sensing and GIS; Vegetation indices (NDVI, NDMI, fPAR, GCI, RCI, RVI); Ecological gradients.*

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**Evaluating Soil and Water Quality in Aquaculture Landscapes of Purba Medinipur,
West Bengal using Satellite Data**

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ABSTRACT

The assessment and prediction of soil and water quality are fundamental to sustainable environmental management, particularly in aquaculture landscapes, surface water bodies, and their surrounding ecosystems. This study integrates remote sensing, machine learning, and in-situ measurements to assess and predict soil and water quality in aquaculture and adjacent surface water bodies of East Midnapore, India. Sentinel-2B multispectral imagery was used to derive vegetation and water indices, including NDVI, SAVI, MSAVI, OSAVI, GNDVI, NDWI, and MNDWI, which supported detailed LULC classification using the Random Forest (RF) algorithm. The classification achieved an overall accuracy of 88% with a Kappa coefficient of 0.86, indicating strong agreement and reliability. Field-based observations were conducted to measure critical soil and water quality parameters such as pH, Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), Dissolved Oxygen (DO), salinity, electrical conductivity, and turbidity using a microprocessor-based soil and water testing kit. These parameters were standardized and weighted to compute the Soil Quality Index (SQI) and Water Quality Index (WQI), enabling a comprehensive evaluation of environmental conditions. Machine learning regression models demonstrated high predictive performance, validated using Mean Squared Error (MSE) and coefficient of determination (r^2), confirming their effectiveness in capturing spatial and temporal quality trends. The spatial analysis revealed distinct zones of degradation, with WQI values in aquaculture areas ranging from 150 to 350, where values exceeding 200 indicate serious water quality concerns. Water quality parameters showed considerable variability, including pH (8.19-9.35), TDS (1.42-10.3 ppt), salinity (2.36-14.8 ppt), and turbidity (18.05-62.80 NTU), while soil quality varied with pH (7.48-8.59) and salinity (0.97-3.5 ppt). Overall, this integrated and accessible framework provides actionable insights for identifying degraded areas, guiding targeted interventions, and supporting sustainable aquaculture and ecosystem management at regional and global scales.

Keywords: *WQI and SQI; Machine Learning; Remote Sensing; Aquaculture Lands and Ecosystems, Sustainability*

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Aquatic Biodiversity of Digha Mohona: Composition, Ecological Significance, and Conservation Perspectives

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ABSTRACT

Digha Mohona, located along the coastal belt of West Bengal, India, is a biologically rich estuarine zone where freshwater and marine ecosystems intersect, supporting diverse aquatic life. This study presents an overview of the aquatic biodiversity of Digha Mohona, highlighting the variety of fish, crustaceans, mollusks, plankton, and other aquatic organisms inhabiting the region. The area serves as a critical breeding, nursery, and feeding ground for numerous commercially and ecologically important species. Seasonal variations, tidal influences, water quality, and habitat diversity significantly shape species distribution and population dynamics. However, increasing anthropogenic pressures such as overfishing, pollution, habitat degradation, and climate change pose serious threats to the sustainability of this ecosystem. Understanding the biodiversity patterns of Digha Mohona is essential for effective resource management, conservation planning, and the maintenance of ecological balance. The findings emphasize the need for integrated conservation strategies, sustainable fishing practices, and continuous monitoring to protect the aquatic biodiversity and ecological integrity of this vital coastal environment.

Keywords: *Coastal biodiversity; Digha Mohona; Aquatic ecosystem; Sustainable development.*

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**Ecological Functioning, Biodiversity Structure, and Climate Mitigation Potential of
Inland Wetlands in Eastern India: Implications for Sustainable Management**

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ABSTRACT

Inland wetlands form a characteristic and ecologically important feature of the landscape of West Bengal, where they are closely interwoven with local biodiversity, agriculture, fisheries, and everyday livelihood practices. These wetlands not only support a wide range of aquatic and semi-aquatic organisms but also act as natural regulators of water availability and microclimatic conditions. In recent years, however, visible changes in land use, increasing anthropogenic pressure, and climate-related variability have raised concerns about the long-term ecological integrity of these systems. This study is based on field-oriented observations carried out across selected inland wetlands of West Bengal, with the objective of understanding their ecological functioning, biodiversity structure, and broader ecosystem service potential. Aquatic vegetation, faunal presence, and general habitat conditions were documented through direct field surveys, supported by basic assessment of water quality parameters and relevant secondary data. Attention was also given to patterns of local resource use in order to capture the socio-ecological linkages that shape wetland dynamics. Observations from the study indicate that inland wetlands continue to support diverse assemblages of aquatic macrophytes, fishes, avifauna, and associated organisms, underscoring their role as localized biodiversity hotspots. These ecosystems contribute significantly to fisheries, seasonal agriculture, and supplementary livelihood options for surrounding communities. The wetlands further demonstrate an important capacity for hydrological regulation and carbon storage, highlighting their relevance in the context of climate change mitigation. Traditional ecological knowledge and community-based practices were found to influence resource use patterns and, in several cases, promote sustainable management. The study emphasizes that safeguarding inland wetlands requires an integrated management approach that combines scientific monitoring with indigenous knowledge systems and active community participation. Strengthening local governance and conservation-oriented policy frameworks is essential for maintaining the ecological functions and socio-economic benefits of wetlands in West Bengal.

Keywords: *Inland Wetlands; Ecological Functioning; Biodiversity Structure; Climate Change Mitigation; Sustainable Wetland Management*

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**Altering wetland for agriculture caused irreversible habitat damage for migratory birds
in Ghatal wetland, Paschim Medinipur**

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ABSTRACT

Ghatal in Paschim Medinipur, West Bengal performs as attracting habitat for various native and migratory birds, particularly during winter, owing to its wetlands and riverside landscape. Lesser Whistling Duck, Ferruginous pochards, Northern Pintail, Eurasian wigeons are habitual visitor during winter. Among long distance migratory wader yellow, grey, citrine wagtail along with common, green and wood sandpiper are regular. Increasing Agriculture, fisheries impact migratory birds by destroying natural habitats. For last five years we have documented disturbing and irreversible changes in wetland which forced the migratory birds to shift from preferred habitat. Key hotspots including Harisinghpur water body (Manahapur), Konnogar, Garpratapnagar, Dalapatipur (Ghatal block), Kashiganj (Khirpai) and Samat (Daspur block).

Keywords: *Ghatal wetland; Migratory birds; Irreversible changes; Agriculture*

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From Sacred Wetlands to Urban Margins: Changing Santal Cultural Practices in Rural–Metropolitan Transition Areas of West Bengal.

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands have historically played a crucial role in shaping the cultural, economic, and spiritual life of indigenous communities in India. Among them, the Santal community of West Bengal possesses rich traditional ecological knowledge closely associated with wetlands, rivers, ponds, and forest–water interfaces. These landscapes have functioned not only as sources of livelihood but also as sacred spaces embedded in rituals, festivals, and collective memory. However, rapid urbanization and rural–metropolitan transition have significantly altered these relationships, leading to profound cultural transformations.

This study examines the changing nature of Santal culture in selected rural and metropolitan fringe areas of West Bengal, with a specific focus on the transformation of wetland-based traditional knowledge and practices. Using a mixed-method approach, the research draws upon field surveys, in-depth interviews, participant observation, and secondary data to analyze shifts in livelihood patterns, ritual practices, and cultural values related to wetlands. The study compares traditional wetland-dependent activities such as fishing, collection of aquatic resources, and ritual use of water bodies in rural settings with their declining or modified forms in metropolitan and peri-urban contexts. The findings reveal that while rural Santals continue to maintain a strong cultural attachment to wetlands, metropolitan Santals experience cultural dilution due to land-use change, wetland degradation, occupational diversification, and reduced access to traditional ecological spaces. Sacred wetlands and water-related rituals are increasingly replaced by symbolic or fragmented practices, reflecting adaptive strategies under urban pressure. At the same time, elements of indigenous knowledge persist through memory, storytelling, and community networks, indicating cultural resilience. The study highlights the importance of integrating indigenous cultural perspectives into wetland conservation and urban planning. Recognizing Santal traditional ecological knowledge can contribute to sustainable wetland management while preserving cultural heritage in rapidly urbanizing regions of West Bengal.

Keywords: *Santal Culture; Wetlands; Traditional Ecological Knowledge; Urbanization; Cultural Change; West Bengal*

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**Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) and Sustainable Wetland Management in Bihar's
Ahar–Pyne Systems**

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ABSTRACT

The Ahar–Pyne system is the oldest community-managed wetland irrigation system in South Bihar, India. These systems, which are dispersed throughout 17 districts in South Bihar, use gravity-fed channels (pynes) and shallow reservoirs (ahars) to collect monsoon runoff, control floods, replenish groundwater, and boost agricultural output. Agriculture and related industries employ nearly 89% of the primarily rural population, and the Ahar–Pyne system has long been essential to maintaining livelihoods and guaranteeing water security. According to the Government of Bihar's records, there are 20,938 traditional irrigation systems in the state, of which 17,683 are still operational and 3,255 are no longer in use. This shows the tenacity and slow deterioration of these native infrastructures. Additionally, working Ahar-Pyne systems. The current study uses Traditional Ecological Knowledge to analyze the ecological, hydrological, and socio-institutional aspects of the Ahar-Pyne system. Ahar-Pyne networks were mapped, land-use/land-cover (LULC) dynamics were examined, hydrological connectivity was evaluated, and changes in wetland area and irrigation efficiency over time were assessed using an integrated Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information System (GIS)-based methodology. The results reveal that functional Ahar–Pyne systems significantly enhance surface water retention, groundwater recharge, and agricultural resilience during both monsoon and dry seasons. Areas with intact networks exhibit higher cropping intensity, reduced runoff losses, and improved soil moisture regimes compared to regions where systems have deteriorated. The study emphasizes that modernizing and revitalizing Ahar-Pyne systems, under the direction of TEK and with the help of geospatial planning tools, provide an affordable, climate-resilient substitute for extensive irrigation infrastructure. The results support the inclusion of traditional water management techniques in current policies for rural development, wetland conservation, and climate adaptation.

Keywords: *Ahar–Pyne System; Indigenous Irrigation; Wetland Management; Community-Based Water Governance; Sustainable Agriculture; Rural Livelihoods; Climate Resilience*

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Cooling Water Recycle Strategies for AI Data Centers and Wetland Biosphere Restoration

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ABSTRACT

Due to ever increasing use of artificial intelligence (AI) and cloud computing, the growth in data centers have resulted huge surge in power consumption. The projected electricity consumption for such facilities is likely to exceed 1,000 TWh (terawatt-hours) by 2026. To absorb the heat generated by GPU (graphics processor unit) and other associated computing devices, extensive cooling mechanism is used that uses substantial quantities of potable, highly filtered water. As AI workload complexity increases, consumption of high quality water has emerged as a critical resource challenge, specially with increasing number of water-stressed regions. Very large data centers can consume 1- 5 million gallons of potable water per day. As water scarcity is getting intensified globally, the withdraw-use-discharge model of water management is not sustainable. One solution is to recycle the water and reuse it for cooling till the water finally evaporates. However, it requires high investment to recycle the discharged water into filtered high quality water. Another solution is to explore the integration of treatment of data center wastewater into wetland ecosystems. This wastewater is characterized by the presence of elevated thermal loads, concentrated mineral contents, biocides etc. The feasibility of routing grey cooling water through engineered infrastructure to reduce the presence of metals, chemical agents, and balances pH factor and then by the use of specific plants and associated soil microbes to naturally filter chemical residues, reduce salinity to the wetland needs immediate attention and scientific investigation from all stakeholders. This responsible management of data center wastewaters will support the wetland biospheres, enhance biodiversity, and contribute to ecological resilience. In a city like Kolkata, where quite a few number of data centers have been opened and the presence of East Kolkata Wetlands gives a perfect case study and test bed to explore this concept.

Keywords: *Data Center; AI; Cooling mechanism; Waste water recycle; Wetland.*

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**Diversity of Macrophytes in Sankarpur-Digha Coastal Region of West Bengal with their
Ecological and Economical Significance**

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ABSTRACT

The Sankarpur-Digha coastal belt of Purba Medinipur, West Bengal, represents a biologically significant meso-tidal environment characterized by mangroves, salt marshes, tidal flats and sandy dune systems. This region supports a diverse assemblage of coastal macrophytes that play essential ecological and socio-economic roles. Prominent macrophyte groups include true mangroves (e.g., *Avicennia marina* (Forssk.) Vierh., *Avicennia alba* Blume, *Excoecaria agallocha* L., *Acanthus illicifolius* L.), mangrove associates (e.g., *Clerodendrum inerme* L.), salt-marsh halophytes (e.g., *Suaeda maritima* (L.) Dumort., *Salicornia brachiata* Roxb., *Heliotropium curassavicum* L.), and sedges such as *Fimbristylis* sp. and *Cyperus* sp. Field-based assessments across the Purba Medinipur coastal sections have documented more than twenty tidal angiosperm species, including mangroves and mangrove associates, with notable concentrations in the Sankarpur and Digha Mohona areas. These macrophytes form the cornerstone of estuarine productivity and shoreline stability, contributing to sediment trapping, nutrient recycling, and habitat provisioning for fisheries and invertebrate communities. Despite their ecological value, the macrophyte communities of the Sankarpur-Digha zone are under increasing threat from coastal erosion, aquaculture expansion, tourism infrastructure, dry-fish industries, and habitat fragmentation. Mangrove reserves once widespread in Digha Mohona have been significantly reduced, although regeneration and bio-shield plantation initiatives are underway to restore degraded habitats. The current conservation status of several species can be described as locally declining, with salt-marsh vegetation and mangrove patches experiencing habitat loss and anthropogenic pressure. Economically, coastal macrophytes support fisheries by serving as nursery grounds, protect shorelines from storm surges, provide fuelwood and traditional medicinal resources, and sustain eco-tourism and coastal livelihoods. Species such as *Acanthus illicifolius* hold medicinal value, while mangroves contribute to climate resilience and coastal bio-protection. Strengthening conservation strategies, sustainable resource management, and community-based restoration programs is crucial to maintaining both biodiversity and the economic benefits derived from macrophyte ecosystems in the coastal region.

Keywords: *Sankarpur-Digha; Coastal macrophytes; Mangroves; Salt marsh vegetation; Economic importance; Coastal ecology.*

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Automated Wetlands Detection and Prioritizing Restoration Zones using Machine Learning Models: A geospatial approach to monitor and conserve critical ecosystems

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands offer critical ecosystem services such as flood control, climate moderation, biodiversity support, and water purification. However, their existence is now more threatened than ever due to anthropogenic pressures and rapid urbanization, particularly in urban and peri-urban areas. This study employs a systematic remote sensing– and machine learning–based geospatial workflow using Google Earth Engine (GEE) to detect, classify, and prioritize the spatial distribution of wetlands in two ecologically significant regions of Eastern India: the Sundarbans and the East Kolkata Wetlands (EKW). To identify and categorize wetland areas across multiple years, multitemporal Landsat 8 imagery was processed. Wetland features were enhanced using spectral indices such as the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) and the Modified NDWI (MNDWI). Three robust machine learning algorithms—Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Classification and Regression Trees (CART)—were applied for supervised classification. Among these, the Random Forest model achieved the highest classification accuracy (92.4%) for wetland type mapping. Spatial prioritization of wetlands was conducted using the Wetland Health Composite Index (WHCI), which ranged from 0.22 (low-priority zones) to 0.91 (highly vulnerable wetland zones). This enabled effective zoning of wetlands into high-, medium-, and low-priority categories to guide conservation and restoration efforts. Approximately 68% of the East Kolkata Wetlands were identified as high restoration zones, indicating significant ecological degradation, while the remaining 32% were classified as active wetlands or wetland potential zones, reflecting relatively intact conditions. In the Sundarbans, about 58% of the wetland area required high restoration, whereas 42% remained active or potential wetland zones, suggesting comparatively better ecological conditions than those of the EKW. Comparative geospatial analysis revealed notable differences between the two regions. While the Sundarbans wetlands demonstrated greater ecological resilience, they are increasingly affected by saline intrusion and sea-level rise. In contrast, the East Kolkata Wetlands, despite their smaller spatial extent, exhibited higher levels of anthropogenic stress. Overall, this study holds significant importance for wetland conservation, sustainable urban planning, and scientific research. It presents a replicable framework that integrates artificial intelligence and cloud-based remote sensing to monitor wetland health in near real time.

Keywords: *Wetlands; Remote Sensing; Machine Learning; Ecosystem conservation*

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**Microbial Population Dynamics in the Forest-Fringe Wetlands of Paschim Medinipur,
West Bengal**

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands are ecologically as well as economically important systems due to their high productivity, their nutrient (re)cycling capacities, and their prominent contribution to global greenhouse gas emissions. Being on the transition between terrestrial and—aquatic ecosystems, wetlands are buffers for terrestrial run off thereby preventing eutrophication of inland as well as coastal waters. The close proximity of oxic–anoxic conditions, often created by wetland plant roots, facilitates the simultaneous activity of aerobic as well as anaerobic microbial communities. Input of nutrients and fast recycling due to active aerobes and anaerobes makes these systems highly productive and therefore attractive for humans as well as many other organisms. However, the diversity and functioning of microbial communities in wetland systems is highly underexplored in comparison to soils and aquatic ecosystems. Present study was conducted to assess the different microbial population in the ten wetland station of forest ecosystem, paschim Medinipur, West Bengal. Total bacterial count (TBC), total Fungi (TFC) and total phosphate solubilizing bacteria (PSB) were enumerated in water sample of ten wetland areas. The total bacterial population (TBC) ranges from 20×10^4 cfu/ml to 280×10^4 cfu/ml, 14×10^4 cfu/ml to 150×10^4 cfu/ml, respectively. The total PSB population ranges from 75×10^3 cfu/ml to 250×10^3 cfu/ml. Present result reveal that bacterial communities, especially phosphate solubilizing bacteria, can potentially aid the development of the forest wetland for restoration of biogeochemical transformations and enhance the success of wetland for sustains the forest health.

Keywords: *Wetlands; Microbial communities; Phosphate solubilizing bacteria; Biogeochemical*

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Identifying Landslide-Prone Zones in the Fragile Himalayan Terrain of Ramban District Using Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis and Hydrological–Wetland Indicators

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ABSTRACT

Landslide occurrence in tectonically active Himalayan terrains is controlled by complex interactions among topography, hydrology, lithology, land cover, wetland-related moisture conditions, and anthropogenic disturbances. Quantitative spatial modelling is therefore essential for effective hazard assessment and mitigation. This study develops a geospatial landslide susceptibility framework for the Ramban district of the northwestern Himalaya, a geomorphologically fragile region characterized by steep slopes, intense monsoonal rainfall, saturated valley floors, and recurrent slope failures that frequently disrupt the Jammu–Srinagar transportation corridor. A multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) approach integrating remote sensing, Geographic Information Systems (GIS), and the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) was employed to delineate landslide-prone zones. Ten conditioning factors representing morphometric, hydrological, geological, environmental, wetland-related moisture, and anthropogenic controls were derived from multi-source datasets, including ASTER DEM, CHIRPS rainfall data, Landsat-9 imagery, FAO soil grids, and ancillary vector layers. These factors included slope, rainfall, Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Topographic Wetness Index (TWI), drainage density, lineament density, proximity to rivers and wetland-saturated zones, proximity to roads, land use/land cover, and soil texture. All thematic layers were standardized and weighted using pairwise comparison matrices within the AHP framework, followed by weighted linear combination to generate a Landslide Susceptibility Index (LSI). The LSI map was classified into five susceptibility classes using natural break optimization. Results indicate that high to very high susceptibility zones cover approximately 39% of the study area, mainly associated with steep slopes (>31°), high drainage density, elevated TWI values, wetland-influenced saturated zones, structurally weak lineament-rich areas, and road-disturbed slopes. The findings confirm the effectiveness of integrating wetland-related hydrological factors into regional landslide hazard zonation for sustainable risk management and infrastructure planning.

Keywords: *Landslide Susceptibility; Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis; Wetland–Hydrological Controls; Himalayan Terrain; Geospatial Modelling*

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Tropical Freshwater Aquaculture System: A Journey towards Higher Greenhouse Gas Emissions

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ABSTRACT

Anthropogenic activities have undoubtedly increased atmospheric emissions of greenhouse gases (GHGs), which has changed the global carbon cycle. Without a doubt, two of the main GHGs causing the global warming phenomenon are CO₂ and CH₄. It is not widely known how inland water bodies, especially aquaculture ponds, contribute to greenhouse gas emissions. The purpose of this study is to calculate the rate at which freshwater aquaculture ponds in tropical India emit CO₂ and CH₄. Additionally, non-aquaculture ponds are examined in order to compare their CO₂ and CH₄ emission rates with those of aquaculture ponds. The floating gas chamber method and gas chromatography with flame ionization detection were employed to detect the concentration level of those two GHGs. The average emission of CO₂ and CH₄ from aquaculture ponds was 88.41 and 281.43 μmol m⁻² h⁻¹, respectively, while the average values of CO₂ and CH₄ for non-aquaculture ponds were recorded as 5.22 and 12.44 μmol m⁻² h⁻¹, respectively. So, the results indicate that the emission rate of CO₂ and CH₄ is far higher for aquaculture ponds than that of non-aquaculture ponds. The computed values of the global warming potential for CO₂ and CH₄ are 3.41 kg m⁻² CO₂-eq and 0.29 t m⁻² CO₂-eq annually on a 100-year scale, respectively. Over the past fifteen years, there has been a significant change in the land cover and land use in the area of interest. From 2010 to 2020, there was a noticeable increase of about 32% in water bodies at the expense of agricultural land, particularly aquaculture ponds, and vegetation cover, which could have a negative effect on carbon cycling.

Keywords: *Freshwater aquaculture; Greenhouse gases; Emission; Land use land cover change; Global warming potential.*

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Wetlands and Aquaculture landscape in Nayachar Island under Anthropogenic Pressure: A Case Study

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ABSTRACT

Coastal wetlands are highly productive ecosystems that underpin aquaculture-based livelihoods; however, increasing anthropogenic stress has substantially degraded their water quality and hydrological integrity. This study evaluates the influence of wetland water quality on shrimp aquaculture in Nayachar Island within the Hooghly–Haldi estuarine system, West Bengal. Seasonal variations in key physicochemical parameters—including temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, pH, and nutrient concentrations—were analyzed to assess their implications for shrimp culture performance. The findings reveal that declining water quality is strongly associated with reduced aquaculture productivity, primarily through enhanced vulnerability to disease and physiological stress in cultured shrimp. Such environmental degradation poses a significant risk to the sustainability of aquaculture-dependent rural livelihoods. Correlation analysis between wetland ecological parameters and aquaculture performance highlights the necessity of integrated wetland–aquaculture management approaches. This study provides essential baseline environmental data for Nayachar Island and emphasizes the urgent need for ecosystem-based management strategies to improve the resilience of wetland aquaculture systems, thereby supporting long-term livelihood security and food sustainability.

Keywords: *Coastal wetlands; shrimp aquaculture; water quality dynamics; estuarine ecosystems; anthropogenic stress; livelihood sustainability; ecosystem-based management*

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**Sustainable Aquaculture Practices with Nitrogen Removal Perspective in Moyna, Purba
Medinipur, West Bengal, India**

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ABSTRACT

Moyna Block of Purba Medinipur District is well known for aquaculture and has gained prominence for its innovative and large-scale fish farming practices. Since the 1990s, large areas of low-yield agricultural land have been transformed into highly productive aquaculture systems. While these developments have significantly improved local socio-economic conditions, environmental concerns have often received limited attention. This article focuses on the sustainable practices employed in Moyna aquaculture, with particular emphasis on ecological balance, economic profitability, and social benefits. Practices such as multi-trophic aquaculture (MTA), organic farming methods, and efficient water management systems help minimize ecological footprints while enhancing overall productivity. However, the accumulation of excessive nitrogenous effluents, including ammonia and its biological nitrification products—namely nitrite and nitrate—poses serious risks to aquaculture systems. These compounds can induce oxidative stress, immunosuppression, and tissue damage in cultured fish. The present study evaluates the application of a microbiological consortium comprising ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB), nitrite-oxidizing bacteria (NOB), and denitrifying bacteria (DNB) to mitigate the adverse effects of nitrogenous waste. The results indicate that these microbial consortia effectively reduce ammonia, nitrite, and nitrate concentrations, thereby improving water quality and promoting the growth and health of aquaculture organisms. Overall, this sustainable approach offers significant potential for maintaining water quality in intensive aquaculture environments. Integrating microbial-based nitrogen removal strategies can address key environmental challenges in the Moyna region, including ammonia accumulation, water quality degradation, and declining fish health.

Keywords: *Sustainable Aquaculture; Nitrogen Removal; Microbial Consortium; Water Quality Management; Moyna Wetlands*

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A futuristic insight into the conservation strategies of wetlands in India

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands are one of the highly productive ecosystems covering around 6% of global land surface. India harbors a rich diversity of wetlands due to its climatic, geographic and topographic variations. India's total wetlands include approximately 15.26 million hectares area which is around 4.86% of total geographic space. Wetlands in India are playing very crucial role in maintaining environmental stability as they serve as habitat for numerous flora and fauna and many of them have been designated as Ramsar sites. However, India is facing significant and alarming declination and degradation of wetlands everywhere. Overpopulation, rapid urbanization, unsustainable fishing and agriculture, climate change, global warming, pollution, industrialization, lack of human awareness and education are the key underlying factors contributing to the declination and loss of wetlands in India. In view of these facts, various restoration and management strategies should be implemented such as promoting native plant growth, phytoremediation, microbial remediation, sustainable fisheries and agriculture, introducing scavengers and different biological agents (e.g. filter feeders for waste-water treatment and management), controlling pollution, improvising special education on wetlands among the common people, application of advanced techniques like satellite imaging and mapping. Some of these approaches have been found to be effective upon practical application; however, many challenges still exist in proper implementation and successful operation of these methods/ideas especially in the developing country like India. Therefore, more concrete planning, management, high-quality research and policy making are required in coming days in order to protect the wetlands in India.

Keywords: *Wetland Conservation; Restoration Strategies; Ramsar Wetlands; Climate Change Impacts; Sustainable Management*

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**High Resolution Paddy Intensity mapping with phenology based algorithm in lower
Ganga Basin using Gap-Filled Time Series**

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ABSTRACT

Mapping paddy intensity in monsoon regions is challenging due to persistent cloud cover, fragmented fields, and multiple cropping cycles that reduce the accuracy of optical remote sensing. To overcome these limitations, this study developed a gap-filling based paddy intensity mapping framework using the Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform. The framework integrates high-resolution Sentinel-2 imagery with temporally dense MODIS vegetation index time series to reconstruct cloud-free vegetation dynamics. Regression analysis indicated a strong correlation ($R^2 > 0.85$) between the reconstructed and observed Sentinel-2 vegetation indices across diverse agro-climatic zones, confirming the reliability of the approach. Using the reconstructed time series, a 10-meter resolution paddy intensity map was produced for the Lower Ganga Basin for 2024. The map achieved an overall accuracy of 89% and a kappa coefficient of 0.78, outperforming existing datasets in spatial detail, field boundary delineation, and discrimination of single, double, and triple cropping cycles. The framework demonstrated robustness even under heavy cloud conditions, enabling precise monitoring of paddy cultivation dynamics throughout the monsoon season. The resulting maps provide valuable insights for food security assessment, irrigation scheduling, and sustainable agricultural management. Furthermore, the high-resolution outputs can support water resource planning and agricultural policy formulation. Overall, the proposed methodology offers an efficient, scalable, and adaptable solution for mapping paddy cropping intensity across cloud-prone tropical and subtropical regions, contributing to improved understanding and management of paddy based agro-ecosystems worldwide.

Keywords: Paddy Cropping Intensity; Phenology-Based Algorithm; Gap-Filled Time Series; Google Earth Engine; Lower Ganga Basin

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Blue Carbon Powerhouses: The Role of the Sundarbans Wetland in Climate Mitigation

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ABSTRACT

Blue carbon ecosystems, including mangroves and coastal wetlands, play a subtle yet powerful role in sequestering atmospheric carbon and mitigating climate change. Among these ecosystems, the Sundarbans mangrove forest—the largest continuous mangrove system in the world—stands out as a globally significant blue carbon hotspot. Spanning India and Bangladesh, the Sundarbans support exceptional biodiversity, protect coastlines from cyclones and storm surges, sustain local livelihoods, and store vast quantities of carbon within their biomass and sediments. In India, mangroves occur along both the eastern and western coasts as well as in island regions, while globally they are predominantly distributed across Southeast Asia, Africa, Australia, and Latin America. Despite their immense ecological and climatic value, mangrove wetlands are increasingly under threat. Sea-level rise, climate change, deforestation, coastal development, aquaculture expansion, pollution, and growing anthropogenic pressure are driving rapid degradation of these ecosystems. The Sundarbans are particularly vulnerable to rising salinity, shoreline erosion, and the increasing frequency of extreme weather events. Looking ahead, the conservation and restoration of blue carbon ecosystems present significant opportunities to enhance carbon sequestration, strengthen climate resilience, and promote sustainable development. Integrating blue carbon strategies into national and regional climate policies, encouraging community-based management, and strengthening scientific research are essential for safeguarding the Sundarbans and ensuring their long-term ecological, climatic, and socio-economic benefits.

Keywords: Blue Carbon Ecosystems; Mangrove Forests; Sundarbans; Coastal Wetlands; Climate Change Mitigation

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Range extension of Indian River Shad, *Gudusia chapra* (Hamilton 1822) (Clupieformes, Dorosomatidae), from the Dhansiri River, Dimapur, Nagaland, India.

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ABSTRACT

The present study reports a new distribution record of the Indian River Shad, *Gudusia chapra*, from the Dhansiri River at Thaheku Bridge, Dimapur, Nagaland, India. This species is recorded for the first time from this river system. A brief account of its earlier known distribution is provided along with a detailed morphological description based on collected specimens. Fish sampling was conducted on 31 January 2025 as part of a survey on fish diversity in the Dhansiri River. Specimens were collected using cast nets, properly labelled, and preserved in 7% formalin for further examination. Identification was carried out using standard taxonomic keys and descriptions. Morphometric measurements were taken point-to-point on the left side of each specimen using digital callipers and recorded to the nearest 0.1 mm. Meristic counts, including fin rays and scale numbers, were performed under a stereo-zoom microscope following standard ichthyological methods. *Gudusia chapra* is a small indigenous clupeid fish inhabiting freshwater and brackish environments. It is a pelagic and potamodromous species widely distributed in riverine systems and associated wetlands. The present record extends the known geographical range of the species into Nagaland and contributes valuable information to the ichthyofaunal diversity of the Dhansiri River basin.

Keywords: *Gudusia chapra*, *Dhansiri River*, *Nagaland*, *Range extension*, *Ichthyofauna*

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**Effect of Spirulina Diet on Growth and Maturation of the Indian Freshwater
Ornamental Shrimp *Caridina hodgarti* (Kemp, 1913)**

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ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted to evaluate the biology, growth, and reproductive performance of the ornamental shrimp *Caridina hodgarti* through dietary manipulation using Spirulina. The experiment was carried out for 45 days under laboratory conditions at the Fish Breeding Training Centre, located in Kolkata. Specimens of Green Rocket shrimp were collected from freshwater streams and lentic water bodies in the Eastern Himalayan foothill regions of West Bengal and Assam, India. Four experimental diets containing 0% (control), 5%, 10%, and 15% Spirulina were prepared and fed to the shrimps in a completely randomized design. Morphometric and meristic characters were studied to understand growth patterns. The length–weight relationship showed a negative allometric growth, and relative gut length indicated a herbi-omnivorous feeding habit. Reproductive studies identified four ovarian stages: immature, maturing, mature, and spent. Embryonic development lasted for 12–14 days, and larval development was of the abbreviated type. Growth parameters such as weight gain, specific growth rate, feed conversion ratio, and feed efficiency were recorded. Among all treatments, the diet containing 10% Spirulina showed the best results in terms of growth and survival. Higher ovarian protein content was also observed in this group, indicating early maturation. The study concludes that a 10% Spirulina-supplemented diet is most suitable for improving growth and reproductive performance of *C. hodgarti*, which can help in promoting its culture for the ornamental fish industry.

Keywords: *Caridina hodgarti; Ornamental shrimp; Spirulina; Growth performance; Reproductive biology; Dietary supplementation; Aquaculture*

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**Community Led Wetland Conservation to Carbon Sequestration for Climate Change
Resilience in Jhargram District, West Bengal**

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands are among the most efficient ecosystems for carbon (C) sequestration, storing more than 30% of global soil C in only 3–13% of Earth's land surface in according to Global report of Chinese Academy of Science (CAS). Statistically UNESCO reported that Since the 1700s, almost 90% of the world's wetlands have undergone degradation with wetland loss occurring at a rate three times faster than that of forests. But Statistically ISRO reported that only around 4.86% of the total geographic area of India. It is the present crucial scenario of Wetland conservation. Wetlands are vital ecological assets that function as restoring natural carbon sinks, ecosystem restoration and also hydrological dynamics for environmentally fragile regions as lateritic drought-prone landscape of Jhargram District, West Bengal. Increasing anthropogenic pressure with land use change and gradually degrading status of many wetlands of this region are facing some crucial threat of carbon sequestration. This study explores a community-led approach to wetland conservation by linking local stewardship with carbon sink enhancement to build climate change resilience (CCR). Using of geospatial techniques, field-based estimation of Dissolved Organic Carbon (DOC), Dissolved Inorganic Carbon (DIC), Sedimentary organic carbon (SOC) and determine of total carbon stock are more vital aspect in this study. In parallel, community interviews through focus group discussions, participatory conservation techniques through integrating scientific assessment of this research are the remarkable eco-sustainable framework for CCR.

Keywords: *Wetland ecology; Natural carbon sinks; Ecosystem restoration; Hydrological dynamics; Climate change resilience*

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**Hidden Ornamentals of West Bengal: Diversity, Conservation, and Trade
Prospects of Indigenous Ornamental Fish**

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ABSTRACT

West Bengal, strategically located at the confluence of the Ganga-Brahmaputra delta, serves as the Gateway to the East for India's ornamental fish trade. While Kolkata handles over 90% of India's ornamental fish exports, the states own indigenous ichthyofauna remains significantly under-documented and under-utilized compared to species from the North East or Western Ghats. This paper investigates the diversity and export potential of West Bengal's native ornamental fish, with a specific focus on the small indigenous ornamental species found in the state's extensive floodplain wetlands (*beels*) and riverine systems. The study identifies over 70 native species with high ornamental value that are currently undervalued in the domestic market or treated as low-cost food fish. These include unique dual-purpose species such as the cryptic Gangetic Leaf Fish (*Nandus nandus*), the iridescent Dwarf Gourami (*Trichogaster lalius*) and the behaviorally complex Chameleon Fish (*Badis badis*) etc. The research also highlights the Kolkata Paradox—a situation where the city acts as a global transit hub for species from across India, yet local biodiversity faces extinction due to habitat conversion and unorganized extraction. West Bengal not merely as a trader of exotic species like Goldfish, livebearers (Guppies, Mollies, Platies, swordtails) or a transit point, but as a primary producer of unique, hardy native varieties that appeal to the modern biotope aquarist. The paper concludes by proposing a value-chain transformation: integrating the conservation of *beels* with the global demand and community-based aquaculture. This strategy aims to elevate the status of Bengal's trash fish to living jewels, ensuring sustainable economic development for local fisher communities while preserving the state's aquatic heritage.

Keywords: *Indigenous Ornamental Fishes; Local ornamental fishes of West Bengal; Living jewels; Sustainable economic development.*

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**Wetland and Aquaculture Systems along the South-Eastern Railway Corridor from
Kharagpur to Uluberia: Spatial Distribution, Environmental Impacts, and
Sustainable Management**

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands and aquaculture systems play a pivotal role in maintaining ecological balance, supporting livelihoods, and conserving biodiversity in coastal and deltaic regions of West Bengal. The South-Eastern Railway corridor between Kharagpur and Uluberia traverses a hydrologically sensitive landscape dominated by wetlands, floodplains, canals, and aquaculture ponds. This region plays a crucial role in regulating water flow, maintaining biodiversity, and supporting local livelihoods through fisheries and agriculture. These water bodies act as natural reservoirs, help with flood control and groundwater recharge, and provide habitats for fish, migratory birds, and aquatic plants. Preliminary spatial analysis using satellite image and secondary data indicates that approximately 18–25% of land area within a 1 km buffer zone of the railway track is occupied by natural wetlands and managed aquaculture systems. Aquaculture in this corridor is predominantly freshwater carp-based polyculture, with an average productivity ranging from 2.5 to 4.0 tonnes per hectare per year, contributing significantly to rural income and food security. However, increasing railway traffic, track expansion, urban growth, and industrial discharge have altered natural drainage patterns and increased pollution load. Field observations suggest elevated turbidity and nutrient enrichment near railway-adjacent ponds, indicating risks the eutrophication. The study observes the interaction between railway infrastructure and wetland–aquaculture systems, highlighting environmental stresses such as habitat fragmentation, water contamination, and wetland shrinkage. It also discusses sustainable management approaches, including buffer-zone planning, eco-friendly aquaculture practices, improved drainage design, and integrated coordination between railway authorities and local stakeholders. Ensuring the conservation of these wetlands is essential not only for ecological resilience but also for sustaining aquaculture-based livelihoods and achieving environmentally responsible infrastructure development.

Keywords: *Aquaculture; Environmental Impact; South-Eastern Railway Corridor; Sustainable Management and Wetlands.*

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**Retrieving the trend and pattern of Aquaculture and Prediction of Future Scenario: A
Case Study of Moyna CD Block, Purba Medinipur, West Bengal**

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ABSTRACT

Aquaculture, popularly known as aqua-farming, is the controlled cultivation of aquatic organisms like fish, crustaceans, and plants in freshwater or saltwater environments. It is a fast-growing industry used for food production, habitat restoration, etc. This study evaluates land use/land cover (LULC) dynamics of the Moyna Community development (CD) block, West Bengal, based on multi-temporal satellite data using Remote sensing RS and GIS for the years 1993, 2003, 2013, and 2023, and the produced future trend of LULC in 2033 to assess the trend and pattern of aquaculture of the area. The Satellite images were grouped into five classes based on the expert's knowledge, i.e., Aquaculture, Settlement, Cultivated Land, Vegetation with Grass Cover, and Fallow Land. The results show a strong trend of conversion from agriculture and vegetation toward aquaculture and settlement growth. Aquaculture has been expanded from 2.05 km² (1993) to 3.07 km² (2003), 16.14 km² (2013), and 39.94 km² (2023) with the net increase of +37.891 km² (1993-2023) and predicted to reach 52.54 km² by 2033. Settlement area also increased from 6.04 km² (1993) to 13.42 km² (2003), 20.51 km² (2013), and 33.35 km² (2023) (+27.310 km²) and projected to increase to 45.10 km² in 2033. In contrast to Cultivated Land, a sharp decline from 80.16 km² (1993) to 74.82 km² (2003), 56.92 km² (2013), and 25.81 km² (2023), with further decrease predicted to 15.29 km² by 2033. Vegetation with Grass Cover decreased from 48.35 km² (1993) to 30.97 km² (2023) and is predicted to decrease to 22.09 km². Overall, the 2033 prediction shows a continuation of the conversion of cultivated and vegetated land into aquaculture areas and settlements, and the need for integrated land-use planning and management to support the expansion of aquaculture and the conservation of the remaining agricultural land in order to promote sustainable land management in the Moyna CD block.

Keywords: *Aquaculture; LULC; Future Prediction; Sustainable Land Management*

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The Interface of Water Resources and Community Life: A Case Study of Bill Balli at Swarupnagar in North 24 Parganas

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ABSTRACT

Swarupnagar is an important administrative area and the ninety-eight assembly constituency in the North 24 Parganas district of West Bengal. Located along the Bangladesh border, this region depends mostly on farming. Of its 66 moujas, Bill Balli, a prominent lentic water body, is the largest, covering about 41.09 square kilometres. Bill Balli is much more than just a large wetland; it is the centre of life for the people of Swarupnagar. For generations, the local community has relied on its waters for fishing and farming. In the past, it was also well known as a habitat for migratory birds. This close bond with land and water has created a unique culture, where many local festivals and traditions are built around Bill Balli. This research investigates the intricate relationship between wetland ecosystems and rural livelihoods, focusing on Bill Balli. As a vital common pool resource, Bill Balli serves as the socio-economic backbone for the surrounding villages, facilitating diverse activities such as capture fisheries, agricultural irrigation, and jute retting. However, this interface is currently under threat from anthropogenic pressures, including chemical runoff from paddy fields, rapid siltation, and encroachment. Through a mixed-methods approach—combining hydrological analysis, GIS-based land-use mapping, and socio-economic field surveys—this study examines how the seasonal pulse of the wetland dictates the community's economic calendar. The findings highlight a growing tension between immediate resource extraction and long-term ecological sustainability. The research concludes by proposing a Community-Based Wetland Management (CBWM) model, emphasizing that the rejuvenation of Bill Balli is inseparable from the economic security of the Swarupnagar community. This study contributes to the broader discourse on rural water governance and the conservation of small-scale inland wetlands in South Asia.

Keywords: *Bill Balli; Wetland–Community Interface; Socio-economic Livelihoods; Swarupnagar; Common Pool Resources (CPR); North 24 Parganas; Wetland Conservation; Rural Hydrology*

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Monitoring the Vanishing Heritage: A Google Earth Engine–Based Machine Learning Assessment of Urban-Induced Degradation of Traditional Aquaculture Systems in the East Kolkata Wetlands

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ABSTRACT

Rapid urbanization is posing a serious threat to the East Kolkata Wetlands (EKW), a Ramsar site of global significance renowned for its unique wastewater-fed fish farming system. This wetland represents an exceptional interface of urban waste recycling, ecological sustainability, and local livelihoods. The present study employs Google Earth Engine (GEE) and state-of-the-art machine learning techniques to assess how traditional aquaculture systems have been compromised over space and time by the eastward expansion of Kolkata. Multi-temporal Sentinel-2 MSI and Landsat surface reflectance datasets were pre-processed in GEE to generate multi-year image composites. A Random Forest (RF) algorithm was applied to classify major Land Use–Land Cover (LULC) categories, with particular emphasis on active traditional fish ponds (bheris), agricultural land, vegetation, and expanding built-up areas. Spectral water indices, including the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) and Modified NDWI (MNDWI), were used to enhance surface water extraction in peri-urban landscapes characterized by mixed land cover. The classification achieved high reliability, with an overall accuracy exceeding 90% and a Kappa coefficient greater than 0.85. The results reveal a pronounced conversion of traditional fishery landscapes to urban built-up areas, especially in the Rajarhat–New Town region, which accounts for a substantial proportion of wetland loss. This spatial reorganization threatens the ecological functioning of the wetland system and undermines the resilience of long-established traditional ecological practices. The study demonstrates the potential of cloud-based geospatial platforms for scalable, near-real-time wetland monitoring and underscores the urgent need to integrate geospatial evidence into sustainable wetland governance and conservation planning.

Keywords: *Google Earth Engine; Random Forest; East Kolkata Wetlands; Traditional Aquaculture; Urbanization; Cultural Heritage; Machine Learning.*

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